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D3.1 Firm-level technology adoption and the rise of Superstar Firms

WP3 Digital Transformation: Impact on skills and inequality

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Frontier Technology Adopters and the Aggregate Decline of Routine Jobs *

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Abstract

This paper highlights the nuanced relationship between firms' technology adoption and the employment structure of the economy. Leveraging a novel firm survey that we link to German administrative employment records, we categorize firms based on their technology adoption status. We find that frontier technology adopters significantly contribute to the economy-wide decline in routine and rise of non-routine cognitive jobs, primarily through firms with complementary workforce skills. Our results suggest (1) a continued de-routinization with frontier technology adoption, (2) the importance of complementary skills for the decline of routine jobs, and (3) a fallacy of drawing economy-wide conclusions from within-firm workforce adjustments.

Keywords: technology, automation, occupational composition, decomposition

JEL: J21, J23, J24, O33

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1 Introduction

An extensive body of literature shows that, starting in the 1980s, computerization has replaced workers in routine codifiable tasks (Autor et al., 2003; Acemoglu and Autor, 2011), leading to an increasing share of workers employed in non-routine occupations at both the lower and upper end of the wage distribution, also referred to as de-routinization (Goos et al., 2009, 2014; Cortes, 2016). Recently, the rapid evolution of new technologies, particularly artificial intelligence (AI), has sparked questions about whether these emerging frontier technologies might increasingly substitute non-routine tasks (Brynjolfsson et al., 2018; Webb, 2020).¹ Yet, the contribution of frontier technologies to the changing employment structure of the economy depends not only on the average workforce adjustments within firms adopting new technologies but also on how adopters differ from non-adopters and the varying abilities of adopting firms to effectively implement these technologies. As Seamans and Raj (2019) have emphasized, a significant challenge in differentiating these adjustment margins is the paucity of comprehensive firm-level data on frontier technology adoption.

In this paper, we quantify these adjustment margins, thereby providing the most comprehensive picture to date of the role of firm-level adoption of frontier technologies for aggregate changes in occupational employment structure, particularly between routine and non-routine occupations. Empirical evidence on the relevance of different adjustment margins is crucial from a policy perspective. A strong decline of routine jobs within adopting firms suggests that frontier technologies inherently displace routine jobs, requiring policies that facilitate this structural transition. If, instead, aggregate employment changes stem from shifts between adopters and non-adopters, this points towards rising inequality between adopters and non-adopters that could be counteracted by policies supporting widespread technology adoption. By contrast, if de-routinization is driven by a subset of frontier technology adopters, it underscores the critical role of firm-specific factors in determining the adoption and impact of frontier technologies.

We shed light on the role of these different margins by collecting novel data on the actual adoption of frontier technologies among 2,032 German manufacturing and service firms, which we link to administrative social security records of all workers employed at the surveyed firms.

¹While several studies have quantified the exposure of job tasks to be substituted by frontier technology such as AI (Acemoglu et al., 2022b; Brynjolfsson et al., 2018; Felten et al., 2018; Webb, 2020), the actual impact on jobs is contingent on various factors including changes in tasks within occupations, job re-organization within firms, cost efficiency, and ethical and legal constraints on task substitution. To date, only a limited number of studies document firm-level adoption and diffusion of the latest frontier technologies (McElheran et al., 2024; Zolas et al., 2020; Genz et al., 2021).

Our data allow us to distinguish between non-investing firms (*non-adopters*), firms investing predominantly in mature digital technologies such as computers and robots (*digital adopters*), and firms primarily investing in frontier technologies such as AI, augmented reality, smart factories, or cloud computing (*frontier adopters*). By leveraging granular occupational information from administrative employment records, we analyze the evolution of workforce composition over time in relation to firms' technology adoption.

Based on this unique data, we first study whether and how frontier technology adopters contribute to the ongoing decline of routine jobs in the German economy. Previous research has documented a decline of approximately 20 percentage points in routine jobs over the past four decades (Bachmann et al., 2019; Goos et al., 2014). Consistent with this implied annual de-routinization rate, our findings indicate a 2.4 percentage points decline in routine jobs alongside a 1.8 percentage points rise in non-routine cognitive jobs between 2011 and 2016. Through a decomposition exercise that builds on Autor et al. (2020) and Acemoglu et al. (2020), we reveal that frontier adopters contribute the most to these employment shifts, followed by firms adopting digital technologies. The continued decline in routine jobs stemming from frontier technology adoption is remarkable, considering that several studies hypothesize that these technologies reduce non-routine cognitive work for the first time (Brynjolfsson et al., 2018; Webb, 2020).

Our decomposition further reveals that the contribution of frontier adopters to the economy-wide de-routinization cannot be attributed to stark differences between frontier technology adopters and digital adopters. In fact, adopters of both technology types are remarkably similar in many respects and differ mainly in observable characteristics that are irrelevant for de-routinization.

Most importantly, we provide evidence that the aggregate employment shift induced by frontier adopters is not reflected in an average decline of routine employment within these firms. In fact, the average frontier firm even (insignificantly) increases its share of routine workers. The aggregate routine-replacing effect of frontier adopting firms instead stems from a subset of these firms: initially larger frontier adopters experience a faster reduction in routine employment compared to the group average, and frontier adopters with an initially less routine-intensive workforce experience faster employment growth. This finding implies that average workforce adjustments among frontier adopters severely underestimate the total contribution of frontier adopters to the economy-wide decline of routine jobs. Moreover, this raises questions about the underlying causes of this heterogeneity.

In a final step, we run firm-level regressions to investigate whether firm-specific factors other than size and initial workforce structure explain the heterogeneous contributions of frontier adopters to employment shifts. The pronounced decline of routine jobs among large frontier adopters remains robust even after controlling for a rich set of firm and workforce characteristics, as well as the firm’s capital structure. However, when we account for differences in how firms perceive changing skill demands and related training needs, firm size no longer significantly contributes to the decline in the share of routine employment. This suggests that large firms are better equipped to identify and implement complementary investments in the skills of their workforce when adopting frontier technologies. Moreover, the stronger employment growth observed for initially less routine-intensive frontier adopters persists even after accounting for a wide range of observable characteristics. Firms that were initially specialized in non-routine cognitive jobs experience faster employment growth, highlighting the importance of occupational specialization for leveraging the benefits of frontier technology adoption. Taken together, our findings support the critical importance of having or establishing a workforce that is complementary to frontier technologies. Frontier adopters that either possess a complementary workforce structure from the outset, or are better equipped to invest in workers’ skills, contribute the most to the shift from routine to non-routine cognitive jobs in the overall economy.

Our paper is related to three literature strands. First, we contribute to the long-standing literature on aggregate changes in the employment structure in response to technology shocks, measured at the industry, region, or country level. The literature on routine-replacing technological change indicates that computerization (which is comparable to our definition of digital technologies) induces a decline in the overall share of workers in routine occupations in the economy (see, e.g., Autor et al., 2003; Goos et al., 2009; Acemoglu and Autor, 2011; Autor and Dorn, 2013; Goos et al., 2014; Cirillo et al., 2021). Another related strand focuses on the adoption of industrial robots (which is a specific digital technology used only by manufacturers) and documents employment shifts across industries and regions (see, e.g., Graetz and Michaels, 2018; Acemoglu and Restrepo, 2020; Dauth et al., 2021). In comparison, we are the first to provide micro-founded evidence on how the diffusion of frontier technologies affects the occupational composition of the aggregate economy. The continued decline in routine jobs stemming from frontier technology adoption is an important novel insight for this literature, since several studies hypothesize that these technologies reduce non-routine cognitive work for the first time (Brynjolfsson et al., 2018; Webb, 2020).

Secondly, we contribute to the recent literature focusing on how *firm*-level technology adoption affects the firm’s employment composition. Corresponding studies examine the impact of firm-level ICT investments (Bartel et al., 2007; Böckerman et al., 2019; Gaggl and Wright, 2017; DeStefano et al., 2018), robot adoption (Acemoglu et al., 2020; Bonfiglioli et al., 2020; Dixon et al., 2021; Humlum, 2019; Koch et al., 2021) and investments into automation technologies more generally (Aghion et al., 2020; Bessen et al., 2020; Domini et al., 2021). Recent studies look at the impact of artificial intelligence (Acemoglu et al., 2022a,b; Zolas et al., 2020; McElheran et al., 2024). Overall, these studies find that firm-level technology adoption enforces organizational change that coincides with labor demand shifts towards non-routine, more skilled, and better-paid workers, but also higher inequality between workers within the firm.² We contribute to this literature by differentiating between mature digital technologies and frontier technologies, focusing on firms from both manufacturing and service industries. We further contribute by quantifying the role of firm-level frontier technology adoption for the overall decline of routine jobs in the economy. Our findings reveal that the routine-replacing effect of frontier technologies relies on complementary skills. This aligns with recent studies emphasizing the importance of favorable firm conditions, such as the presence of skilled workers and complementary innovations, like reorganization of work, to fully realize gains from new technological capabilities (Ransbotham et al., 2017; Brynjolfsson et al., 2019, 2021; Ciarli et al., 2021; Harrigan et al., 2024).

Finally, we contribute to the emerging literature on the sources of inequality between and within firms. Previous studies show that employment reallocation within and between firms contributes to the changing occupational structure, often referred to as job polarization (Kerr et al., 2020; Harrigan et al., 2021). Cortes et al. (2023) argue that technological change leads to higher employment concentration in more productive firms and an increase in between-firm wage inequality. Further studies indicate that the falling labor share is driven by employment reallocation between firms, known as the superstar phenomenon (Autor et al., 2020; Acemoglu et al., 2020). Additionally, several papers on firm-level technology adoption document employment shifts within adopting firms (Aghion et al., 2020; Gaggl and Wright, 2017; Domini et al., 2021). We add to this literature by documenting employment reallocation related to frontier technology adoption. Our unique data allow us to differentiate employment reallocation that occurs within versus between adoption groups. We demonstrate that occupational adjustments within adopting

²While we concentrate on the employment structure, further studies show positive impacts on firm performance (Bettiol et al., 2019; Cirillo et al., 2022), productivity (Cathles et al., 2020) and innovation activity (Babina et al., 2022; Rammer et al., 2022).

firms play only a minor role in the overall decline of routine work in the economy. Instead, job polarization is driven by a subset of frontier technology adopters, highlighting a new dimension of workplace polarization within the group of technology adopters.

The remainder of this paper proceeds as follows: Section 2 describes the data, develops our technology adoption measure and provides insights into firm-level technology adoption in Germany. Section 3 relies on a decomposition analysis to document a link between overall de-routinization in the economy and firm-level technology adoption, highlighting the crucial role of heterogeneity among adopters of frontier technologies. Section 4 delves into mechanisms behind this heterogeneity and section 5 concludes.

2 Data

2.1 Data sources

For our analysis, we conducted a representative firm survey on technology adoption and linked the results with employment biographies from social security records for all workers employed in the interviewed firms.

Firm survey on technology adoption. We conducted a survey among a representative sample of 2,032 German establishments between March and May 2016, the “IAB-ZEW-Labor Market 4.0-Establishment Survey (BIZA)” to identify the adoption of frontier technologies, as described in the concept discussed below.³ The establishments in our survey are a stratified random sample of all German establishments with at least one employee subject to social security contributions which are registered at the German Federal Employment Agency. The German administrative data contains information on single-location establishments and does not contain information on whether these establishments belong to a multi-site company or not. For simplicity, we refer to these establishments as firms in the remainder of the paper.

The interviews were held with either the production managers or the firms’ general manager and lasted an average of 30 minutes. The survey covers three main topics: (1) the relevance of and perceptions about frontier technologies; (2) the firms’ level of technological advancement; and (3) the firms’ demand for skills and competencies. We collect all information contemporaneously for 2016 and ask for retrospective information for 2011 for several key questions. In particular,

³The data can be accessed at the Research Data Centre (FDZ) of the German Federal Employment Agency, see <https://fdz.iab.de/en/our-data-products/establishment-data/biza/>

we use retrospective information to track the adoption of frontier technologies.

All firms received a written invitation for the survey prior to being contacted for a Computer-Assisted Telephone Interviewing (CATI) session. Among all contacted firms, 2,032 firms completed the survey, yielding a response rate of 31.5%. Non-participation was typically due to general refusal of interviews, especially over the phone, or due to time constraints. The use of modern technologies played only a minor role in non-participation decisions. Genz et al. (2021) provide a detailed analysis of non-participation for the dataset, showing that the surveyed firms are comparable in terms of size, industry, and location to the population of German firms (see Appendix A.1 in Genz et al. (2021)). Hence, our survey is representative of German firms, and potential biases concerning technology adoption, if any, are likely to be small.

Weights. Our sample is stratified by firm size (four categories), region (East/West Germany), and industrial sector (five categories)⁴ and covers both service and manufacturing firms. To ensure sufficient observations, we conducted at least 50 interviews within the resulting 40 cells.⁵ This naturally leads to oversampling of certain cells (relative to the overall population of firms). We correct for oversampling by computing firm stratification weights w_f as the inverse inclusion probability of firms in our survey. Weights are scaled to a mean value of one, such that the sum of weights reflects the number of firms.⁶ We apply the firm stratification weights w_f in empirical analyses which are representative of all German firms, for instance, when we focus on the changes of average employment shares across task domains within firms.

For analyses with a focus on workforce composition, or when firm size matters, we rely on employment weights \tilde{s}_f . In particular, we use the firm stratification weights w_f to compute the employment weights $\tilde{s}_f = \frac{w_f s_f}{\sum_{f' \in F} w_{f'} s_{f'}}$, where s_f is a firm’s share of total employment. We scale these weights to a mean of one analogous to the firm stratification weights. We apply the employment-weighted firm stratification weights \tilde{s}_f in empirical analyses which are representative of the German workforce, for instance, when we analyze changes in the aggregate employment shares across task domains.⁷

⁴See Data Appendix B for details.

⁵We merge the cells for firms with “50-200 employees” and “200 and more employees” in the the East German ICT sector due to the small number of large ICT firms in East Germany.

⁶The sample of firms was drawn in 2014, weights therefore are representative of the 2014 distribution of firms and are time constant.

⁷Depending on the type of analysis, we use either time-varying employment weights based on time-varying employment information or time-constant employment weights based on firms’ initial employment in 2011.

Employment histories. We link our survey data to employment biographies from social security records (IAB Beschäftigtenhistorik (BeH) V10.03.00, Nürnberg 2018) for all workers employed in the surveyed firms between 2011 and 2016. The social security system covers roughly 80% of the German workforce, omitting information about the self-employed and civil servants. The social security records include, among other items, information on workers' employment status, occupation, industry, and earnings.⁸ We transform the data for all workers between 18 and 65 years of age in regular jobs subject to social security contributions to an annual panel between 2011 and 2016.⁹ This implies that the data excludes minor employment, apprentices, and family workers, which leaves 1,191,734 observations for 318,316 employees between 2011 and 2016.

Based on this sample of workers, we calculate the firm's occupation structure and other firm-level indicators such as total employment and average wages. For the occupational composition, we use the main task categorization for occupations by Dengler et al. (2014). They exploit information on competencies and skills from the German expert database BERUFENET of the Federal Employment Agency to calculate the main task type of occupations. We merge the main task type to our data via the occupation code (KldB-2010, 3-digit) to classify occupations and calculate the firms' annual workforce size by task domain, thereby distinguishing between occupations that predominantly use (1) non-routine cognitive (2) routine cognitive and manual, and (3) non-routine manual tasks. This enables us to detect employment shifts from routine occupations to non-routine occupations over time.¹⁰ The occupational classification (KldB-2010, 5-digit) furthermore contains information on job requirement categories that are sorted by increasing complexity. It distinguishes (1) unskilled workers, (2) professionals, (3) specialists, and (4) experts. We prefer this skill measure to a formal education measure because it captures the skills required to perform a job from the employer's perspective. We also calculate the number of workers by age as of 2011 and distinguish between (1) younger than 40, (2) between 40 and 55, and (3) older than 55 years of age.

As a further control variable, we use estimated firm effects from Bellmann et al. (2020), which is an update of Card et al. (2013) for more recent periods. These firm fixed effects are available

⁸Wages are reported only up to the social security contribution limit. We impute wages using Tobit regressions following Card et al. (2013) and Dustmann et al. (2009).

⁹We follow the standard procedure in the literature using German administrative data and rely on employment spells that overlap June 30th of each year.

¹⁰Our measure classifies occupations according to their main task in 2011 and does not capture variation in task content within occupations across time, which has been highlighted as an additional dimension of occupational change (Acemoglu and Autor, 2011; Spitz-Oener, 2006; Freeman et al., 2020; Consoli et al., 2023).

for social security records, and we match them to our sample of firms.

Sample selection. Since we aim to examine firm-level employment shifts across occupations divided into three task domains between 2011 and 2016, we impose several restrictions on the sample of 2,032 surveyed establishments.¹¹ First, we restrict our sample to firms that exist in all years, i.e., that were founded prior to June 30th, 2011, and that are observable in our administrative data until 2016 (-235 firms). In addition, we impose the restriction that these firms have at least one employee subject to social security contributions in regular employment on June 30th, 2011 and 2016 (-122 firms). A further 15 firms are dropped due to missing information on the technology indicators which are at the core of our analysis.¹² These restrictions leave us with 1,660 firms that are observable in our administrative data for the entire observation period, have at least one employee in regular employment across time, and for whom we have information on technology adoption between 2011 and 2016.

2.2 Defining technology adoption

The key advantage of our survey is that it contains a direct firm-level measure of technology adoption. In particular, our survey measures the firms' level of technological advancement in 2016 and 2011 and uses this survey information to classify firms into three adopter groups.

Surveying a firm's level of technological advancement. In order to survey the firms' level of technological advancement, we asked the respondents to classify firms' work equipment (i.e., the fixed assets) into three technology levels that differ in their degree of automation and digitalization, see Table 1. In particular, our conceptual framework distinguishes frontier technologies, computer-controlled technologies, and older manual technologies. The definitions of each of these technology levels are kept rather generic to ensure that the distinction applies to and is comparable across all firms in our sample. To facilitate a common understanding, we give examples of technologies and provide respondents with further examples upon request. Moreover, we measure the technological advancement separately for electronic office and communication (O&C) and production (PROD) equipment to allow for more targeted questions and examples

¹¹There is a structural break in the occupational classification in 2011 that has been harmonized but still might limit the comparability of the task structure across time. Appendix Figure E.1 shows that the results are robust to using 2012 rather than 2011 as the base year for our analysis.

¹²We conduct several robustness checks using alternative sample choices and show that our key findings remain unaltered. The results are displayed in Appendix E.

Table 1: Firms' level of technological advancement

Technology level $g \in \{manual; digital; frontier\}$	Work process organization	Production equipment (k_g^{PROD})	Office and communication equipment ($k_g^{O\&C}$)
Frontier technology (fourth industrial revolution, $g \in \{frontier\}$)	Technology performs work process largely automatically and autonomously	Self-controlled ($k_{frontier}^{PROD}$) e.g., production facilities up to smart factories, cyber-physical systems and internet of things	IT-integrated ($k_{frontier}^{O\&C}$) e.g., analytic tools for big data, cloud computing systems, internet platforms such as Amazon, shop systems or online-markets
Digital technology (third industrial revolution, $g \in \{digital\}$)	Humans are indirectly involved in work process	Indirectly controlled ($k_{digital}^{PROD}$) e.g., CNC machines, industrial robots or process engineering systems	IT-supported ($k_{digital}^{O\&C}$) e.g., computers, terminals, electronic checkout systems or CAD-systems
Manual technology (first and second industrial revolution, $g \in \{manual\}$)	Humans largely conduct work process manually	Manually controlled (k_{manual}^{PROD}) e.g., drilling machine, motor vehicles or X-ray machine	Not IT-supported ($k_{manual}^{O\&C}$) e.g., telephones, fax and copy machines

Notes: The table shows the technology levels as they were defined and explained (including examples) to the interviewees during the CATI-interview. The interviewees were then asked to give an estimate of how their work equipment is divided among these technology levels (in percent).

throughout the survey. This separate assessment of the firm's technology level also accounts for the fact that technological progress need not be implemented at the same pace in both domains.¹³

Manual technologies refer to the lowest technology level and comprise old technology associated with the first and second industrial revolution which requires humans to be largely involved in the work processes. Production equipment in this technology class is manually controlled, such as drilling machines, motor vehicles, or X-ray machines. Office and communication equipment in this class is not IT-supported, such as analogue telephones, faxes, or copy machines.

The intermediate technology level encompasses digital technologies associated with the third industrial revolution, which started to be introduced in the 1980s. It refers to technologies where human involvement in work processes is indirect. These technologies are supported by IT to automate specific sub-processes and facilitate new applications. Production equipment in this class is indirectly controlled, such as CNC machines, industrial robots, or process engineering systems. Similarly, office and communication equipment in this class are IT-supported, including computers, terminals, electronic checkout systems, or CAD systems.

Technologies at the highest level, representing frontier technologies associated with the fourth industrial revolution, are fully integrated into the firms' central IT systems, facilitating largely automated work processes without human intervention. This class includes self-controlled production equipment, such as smart factories, cyber-physical systems, and the Internet of Things.

¹³Since our firm survey includes firms in the service sector, not all surveyed firms use production equipment. Firms without production equipment (61%) assessed only the level of technology of their office and communication equipment.

Moreover, it encompasses IT-integrated office and communication equipment, such as the use of big data, cloud computing, and online markets. The highest technology level hence covers the most recent technologies that we consider to reflect the technological frontier as of 2016.

After providing interviewees with an overview of these technology classes, we ask them to separately assess the share (in percent) of the firm’s production and O&C equipment that is currently based on each of these in 2016. We also ask for a corresponding retrospective assessment for the technology classes in 2011.¹⁴

Note that Genz et al. (2021) correlate the firm-level technology shares from our survey, aggregated to the industry average, with the industry-level ICT capital shares from the EU KLEMS dataset. This dataset includes details on computer hardware, telecommunications equipment together with total capital stocks based on the ISIC Rev. 4 classification. Positive correlations for both digital and frontier technologies, and a negative correlation for manual technologies, bolsters our confidence that our data exhibits plausible patterns compared to existing data sources and technology measures at aggregate levels.

Technology-specific investments. Based on the shares provided during the survey, we calculate the firm’s overall level of technological advancement g , where $g \in \{manual; digital; frontier\}$, at time t in firm f as follows:

$$k_{fgt} = \left((1 - \delta_f) k_{fgt}^{O\&C} + \delta_f k_{fgt}^{PROD} \right) \quad (1)$$

where δ_f equals the time-constant initial-level share of blue-collar workers in the firm that we derive from the administrative employment histories that can be linked with our survey.¹⁵ For simplicity, we refer to firms’ work equipment by technology level as technology shares k_{fgt} . Technology shares add up to unity separately for production and office and communication equipment within each firm and year.

While changes in technology shares are informative about the composition of firms’ technology, they contain limited information on firms’ technology investments since changes in technology shares do not capture those technology investments that yield the relative composition unaltered. To capture differences in the total investment sums, we combine the information on the technology shares k_{fgt} with a measure of the firm’s capital *stock* K_{ft} representing the firm’s fixed assets,

¹⁴Column 1 in Appendix Table A.1 reports the average shares across all responses obtained from the firm survey.

¹⁵The classification is based on 1-digit levels of International Standard Classification of Occupations (ISCO 2008): white-collar (ISCO codes 1 to 5); blue-collar (ISCO codes 6 to 9).

and derive a technology-specific capital stock across time as $K_{fgt} = k_{fgt} \times K_{ft}$. Since we do not observe information on the absolute value of the capital stock at the firm level, we impute capital stock information K_{ft} for the firms in our sample from the IAB Establishment Panel, which requires additional assumptions.¹⁶ The obtained technology-specific capital stocks K_{fgt} allow us to calculate the firm's net investments I_{fg} into technology-specific capital stocks by taking the five-year difference between 2011 and 2016:

$$I_{fg} = \Delta K_{fg} = K_{fgt=2016} - K_{fgt=2011} \quad (2)$$

Classification of adopter groups. We use these net investments I_{fg} to classify firms into three adopter groups $g \in (\textit{non}; \textit{digital}; \textit{frontier})$ depending on their main investments from 2011 to 2016:

$$g\text{-adopter} \iff I_{fg} = \max(I_{f,g=\textit{manual}}, I_{f,g=\textit{digital}}, I_{f,g=\textit{frontier}}) \quad (3)$$

Hence, *non-adopters* mainly invest in older manual technologies, *digital adopters* mainly adopt computer-controlled digital technologies and *frontier adopters* mainly invest in autonomous cutting-edge technologies. A firm belongs to the adopter group $g \in (\textit{non}; \textit{digital}; \textit{frontier})$ (1) if the firm raises its share of g -technologies more than the other shares, irrespective of whether the firm expands or shrinks its capital stock, (2) if the firm leaves the relative technology shares unchanged, but expands its overall capital stock and used primarily g -technologies in 2011, (3) if the firm raises its overall capital stock and simultaneously raises its g -technology share. Hence, our definition considers both initial stocks and changes in technology shares when classifying firms' adoption status. Appendix B provides a formal definition and discusses special cases.

Note that we prefer to classify firms based on the imputed technology-specific changes in capital stocks ΔK_{fg} rather than using the reported changes in technology shares Δk_{fg} . Assigning firms to adoption groups based on technology-specific changes in capital stocks ΔK_{fg} emphasizes firms' initial technology composition, yielding a more stringent classification of frontier adopters.¹⁷

¹⁶See Appendix B for details. Given that the survey was conducted as a CATI, we considered it infeasible to ask for the technology-specific capital stocks across time.

¹⁷In Appendix B we discuss the strengths and weaknesses of both approaches and provide illustrative examples of the assignment into adoption groups. In Appendix Figure E.4, we show a replication of our main results using the alternative approach to assign adoption groups by focusing on changes in technology shares.

2.3 Technology use and adoption in Germany

Table 2 shows that our final sample consists of 525 non-adopters, 962 digital adopters, and 173 frontier adopters when applying the aforementioned classification. Frontier adopters only represent 7.9% of all German firms, but 10.4% of all workers in 2011 (see Panel C). Thus, only a small fraction of frontier firms predominantly invests in the most recent technologies such as augmented reality, smart factories, or cloud computing, while most German firms focus on either computer-controlled digital technologies or even older manual technologies.

Table 2: Technology use and employment growth across German firms

	All		non-adopters		digital adopters		frontier adopters	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
<i>Panel A: Technology-specific capital stock in 2011 (in 1,000 €) and in %</i>								
manual tech	72.6	46.9%	59.0	71.2%	82.3	40.2%	88.9	35.2%
digital tech	71.7	46.3%	20.1	24.3%	112.5	54.9%	109.9	43.5%
frontier tech	10.7	6.9%	3.7	4.5%	10.0	4.9%	53.9	21.3%
<i>Panel B: Technology-specific capital stock in 2016 (in 1,000 €) and in %</i>								
manual tech	111.7	38.4%	116.1	70.9%	110.9	28.7%	91.4	21.7%
digital tech	148.7	51.1%	40.4	24.7%	246.0	63.7%	160.8	38.2%
frontier tech	30.6	10.5%	7.1	4.4%	29.4	7.6%	168.5	40.0%
<i>Panel C: Representing number of firms and workers</i>								
# firms (in K)	1925.1	100.0%	848.4	44.1%	924.7	48.0%	151.9	7.9%
# workers in 2011 (in M)	27.9	100.0%	8.9	32.0%	16.1	57.6%	2.9	10.4%
# workers in 2016 (in M)	31.5	100.0%	10.0	31.7%	18.3	58.2%	3.2	10.2%
Observations	1,660		525		963		172	

Notes: Table shows mean statistics weighted with firm stratification weights. In Panel A and Panel B uneven columns give the capital stock in 1,000 € and even columns give the relative shares of the capital stocks across technology classes in % adding up to 100 per column. In Panel C uneven columns give the number of firms or workers employed in M and even columns give the relative shares of firms or workers across non-adopting and adopting firms in % adding up to 100 per row. Note that the number of firms is time-constant due to the balanced panel of firms, see section 2.1.

Table 2 also provides information on the technology usage across all firms and by adoption group in 2011 (Panel A) and 2016 (Panel B) both in absolute levels (uneven columns) and percentage shares (even columns).¹⁸ In 2011, the average German firm mostly employed older manual technologies, but predominantly used digital technologies in 2016. In fact, the average firm mainly invested in digital and frontier technologies at the expense of older technologies during that time period (see columns 1-2). Frontier technologies play a small but growing role in the German economy with more than 10% of the average firm's capital stock being based on

¹⁸Note that these are not identical to the technology-specific capital shares k_{fgt} from the survey. For comparison, these can be found in Appendix Table A.1.

frontier technologies in 2016 compared to 7% in 2011.¹⁹

Columns 3-8 document distinct patterns of technology use by adoption group. Panel A shows that the initial capital stock of non-adopting firms predominantly consist of older manual technology (column 3), which accounts for more than two-thirds of their technology (column 4). Moreover, investments until 2016 left the technology distribution unchanged. In contrast, frontier and digital adopters predominantly used digital technologies in 2011 (columns 5 and 7). With respect to the initial use of and investments into frontier technologies, digital and frontier adopters clearly differ: while for digital adopters frontier technologies in 2011 only account for 5% of the capital stock (Panel A, column 6), they already represent more than 20% among frontier adopters (Panel A, columns 8). Both adopter groups extended the share of frontier technologies until 2016, although frontier adopters invested much more in frontier compared to digital technologies, in absolute terms. In 2016, frontier technologies represent 40% of the capital stock of the average frontier adopter (Panel B, column 8), while the corresponding share remains rather low with 7.6% for digital adopters (Panel B, column 6).²⁰ Hence, the adopter groups resulting from our classification differ significantly in their capital structure.²¹

In line with the existing literature, we document that non-adopters differ significantly from technology adopters (of either digital or frontier technologies). Adopters are larger, more often service firms, and employ at the outset more routine and fewer unskilled workers (see Appendix Table B.2). Our data even enables us to examine differences in observable characteristics between firms adopting digital versus frontier technologies. Remarkably, we find only few differences between the two adoption groups: Manufacturing firms and those with an older workforce are less likely to adopt frontier compared to digital technologies. Further, the availability of high-speed internet access is positively associated with frontier technology adoption.

In the remainder of the paper, we use the three groups, non-adopters, digital adopters and frontier adopters to examine whether and how these adoption groups contribute to changes in the German occupational composition.

¹⁹Appendix Table A.2 shows that these average technology patterns are similar when differentiating between manufacturing and service firms.

²⁰In line with our study, Acemoglu et al. (2022a) find that the adoption of AI, robotics, dedicated equipment, specialized software, and cloud computing remains low across firms in the U.S.

²¹Appendix Table A.3 also shows differences in initial firm and workforce characteristics by adoption group.

3 De-routinization in the German economy

In this section, we aim to understand how firm-level technology adoption contributes to changes in the occupational composition of the German economy. We start by examining occupational shifts in the economy, before assessing the subsequent contributions of non-adopters, digital adopters, and frontier adopters.

3.1 Aggregate de-routinization in Germany

Aggregate decline in routine jobs since 1975. Previous research has documented large changes in the structure of employment over the past four decades in developed countries (Goos and Manning, 2007), including Germany (Goos et al., 2014). Bachmann et al. (2019) document a sharp decline in the employment share of routine jobs by 21 percentage points between 1975 and 2014, or 0.5 percentage points on an annual basis. By contrast, they find an increase in the employment shares of non-routine manual jobs by 8 percentage points (0.2 percentage points per year) and a 13 percentage points (0.33 percentage points per year) increase in the share of non-routine cognitive jobs. This is in line with the existing evidence for other countries.

Aggregate decline in routine jobs between 2011 and 2016. For the time period between 2011 and 2016, Figure 1(a) documents a substantial decline in routine cognitive and routine manual (RC/RM) jobs by about 2.4 percentage points among the German workforce. This decline is mostly compensated by rising non-routine cognitive (NRC) employment shares (+1.8 percentage points) and to a smaller extent by rising non-routine manual (NRM) employment shares (+0.6 percentage points). The observed shifts are thus well in line with the annual shifts reported for previous years. They are also consistent with the literature that suggests that technology adoption aims to substitute for human labor in routine, replaceable tasks, while complementing workers in non-routine, non-replaceable tasks (Acemoglu and Autor, 2011).

Routine jobs decrease significantly in the workforce of frontier adopters. The key advantage of our data is that we can distinguish those shifts by adoption group (non-adopters, digital adopters, and frontier adopters) and trace occupational employment shifts at the firm level. Hence, Figure 1(b) shows the change between 2011 and 2016 in the share of workers that belong to a certain task group and are employed at the respective adoption group, for example, frontier adopters. The proportion of routine jobs decreases the most in the workforce of frontier adopters,

Figure 1: De-routinization in the aggregate and by adoption group between 2011 and 2016

Notes: Panel (a) shows aggregate occupational shifts by task domain for the entire German workforce; Panel (b) depicts the change in the share of occupations by task domain among the workforce employed at adoption group g . Weighted with time-varying employment-weighted firm stratification weights \tilde{s}_f . Appendix Figure D.5 panel (a) displays how the shifts observed in panel (b) for each adoption group g contribute to the aggregated occupational shifts by accounting for the initial distribution of firms across adoption groups (see Table 2). NRC: non-routine cognitive jobs; RC/RM: routine cognitive/manual jobs; NRM: non-routine manual jobs. Confidence bands based on jackknife standard errors.

followed by a somewhat smaller decline in the proportion of routine jobs in the workforce of digital adopters. Moreover, de-routinization among both adopter groups is accompanied by an increasing proportion of workers who are employed in non-routine cognitive jobs. Figure 1(b) thus provides evidence that, contrary to recent expectations (Webb, 2020; Brynjolfsson et al., 2018), adopters of frontier technologies contribute significantly to aggregate de-routinization.²²

Interestingly, de-routinization occurs among all adoption groups including non-adopters, though not statistically significant. This indicates that de-routinization is partly driven by forces other than technological change, such as domestic outsourcing (Cortes and Salvatori, 2019), offshoring (Reijnders and de Vries, 2018), or changes in consumer demand (Autor and Dorn, 2013). Contrary to adopters, de-routinization among non-adopters favors non-routine manual rather than non-routine cognitive jobs.

²²In an additional analysis, we show that these occupational employment shifts are accompanied by shifts between skill groups (Appendix Figure D.7) and wage groups (Appendix Figure D.8). In particular, we find a clear trend towards skill and wage polarization: Both the highest and the lowest skill group (wage group) increase at the expense of the medium skill group (wage group). However, the increase in experts and high-paid jobs group is solely driven by frontier adopters while the increase in helpers and low-paid jobs group is also driven by non-adopters and digital adopters.

3.2 Economic reasoning about the sources of de-routinization

The observed aggregate decline in routine employment suggests that frontier technologies contribute significantly to recent de-routinization. Yet, three potential channels may drive this outcome. These channels come with different implications, which is why it is important to analyze the relevance of each channel:

Channel 1: Direct routine replacement within technology-adopting firms. The RRTC literature builds on the idea that computer-controlled technologies induce shifts *within firms* due to capital-labor substitution, reducing the shares of routine, unskilled, and low-paid workers within firms. Several studies find empirical evidence that firm-level technology investments in ICT technology and industrial robots are associated with or induce labor demand shifts towards non-routine, more skilled, and better-paid workers who are complementary to the new technologies (Gaggl and Wright, 2017; Böckerman et al., 2019; Acemoglu et al., 2020; Bonfiglioli et al., 2020; Humlum, 2019; Koch et al., 2021). Yet, it remains an open question whether the rapidly emerging frontier technologies, such as AI, smart factories, and cloud computing, lead to job displacement within adopting firms and which occupation group will be most exposed (Brynjolfsson et al., 2018; Webb, 2020).²³ If the average employment shift observed within frontier adopters – the *within firms* effect - resembled the pattern in Figure 1(b), this would suggest widespread replacement of routine jobs within adopting firms, irrespective of firm-specific conditions. A strong within firm component would imply that the adoption of frontier technologies is routine-replacing per se. This might point to a substantial demand shift across occupations in the long-run and the need for policies facilitating this structural transition.

Channel 2: Employment reallocation between adoption groups. The RRTC literature discusses a second mechanism that may induce employment shifts between firms: initial heterogeneity in firm size and employment structure between technology-adopting and non-adopting firms. This mechanism is based on the idea that technology adoption enables adopting firms to grow faster. Numerous studies confirm that firms adopting automation technologies experience

²³Acemoglu et al. (2022b) link AI exposure to changes in skills demanded by establishments in job postings, finding that AI technology alters the task structure of jobs by generating new tasks accompanied by new skill demands. Acemoglu et al. (2022a) find suggestive evidence for skill upgrading by firms using advanced technologies, though their data does not allow to quantify the contribution of technology adoption at the firm level to overall occupational shifts. We complement these recent studies by linking the firm-level adoption of frontier technologies to occupational employment shifts in the entire economy and thereby quantifying their contribution to de-routinization at the firm level and in the total economy.

faster employment growth than non-adopting firms (Bessen et al., 2020; Acemoglu et al., 2020; Koch et al., 2021; Domini et al., 2021). Consequently, this faster employment growth may result in a *between adoption groups* effect, altering the aggregate occupational composition if adopters and non-adopters differ substantially in their workforce composition. Harrigan and Reshef (2015) similarly present a theoretical model that combines firm heterogeneity in productivity with firm heterogeneity in skill structures to show how trade raises inequality by shifting demand towards technology-adopting skill-intensive firms. Therefore, a strong between adoption group component would point towards rising inequality between adopters and non-adopters. Since several studies suggest that successful technology adoption leads to an increase in market exits of non-adopters, this underscores the need for policies that support employees in the event of plant closures and to promote widespread technology adoption.

Channel 3: Employment reallocation within adoption groups. As a third channel, the intensity of de-routinization induced by technology adoption might vary between firms within the group of frontier adopters. If frontier adopters are heterogeneous with respect to the initial conditions when adopting new technologies, we might find stronger substitution in places where related adjustments are more beneficial and easier to implement. For instance, technology adoption requires technologically skilled workers (Harrigan et al., 2024) and complementary investments into training and organizational change (Brynjolfsson and Hitt, 2000; Bresnahan et al., 2002; Brynjolfsson and Milgrom, 2013), as it is usually not sufficient to buy off-the-shelf technologies and adopt it in the previous environment without any accompanying adjustments. Firms may be differently equipped for such investments and restructuring. This can induce a *within adoption groups* effect, i.e., a shift in aggregate employment shares that occurs due to compositional changes between technology-adopting firms. In fact, Cortes et al. (2023) combine a Melitz (2003) type model with skills and task-biased technological change (TBTC) and find that task changes differ in intensity also within the group of adopters depending on their size and productivity. This view is also in line with Battisti et al. (2023) who find that the combination of technologies with organizational change is associated with changes in tasks.

This heterogeneity between adopter firms could itself be either due to *scale effects* or due to *composition effects*. Scale effects occur when the change in the occupation structure differs between firms that differ in initial firm size – for example larger declines of routine jobs in larger firms. Composition effects occur when firms with different initial occupational employment

structures experience differences in employment growth – for example, faster growth among non-routine-intensive firms.

A pronounced within adoption groups effect would thus point to specific conditions that are necessary for frontier technologies to be routine replacing. Hence, a within adoption groups effect could reveal the conditions under which frontier technologies are profoundly routine replacing and under which conditions the adoption does not or only moderately replaces routine work. Identifying these factors is crucial for understanding and addressing the between-firm heterogeneity among frontier technology adopters, providing insights on how to mitigate this disparity.

Which of the three main channels (and sub-channels) contributes most to de-routinization is an important empirical question. Whether the contribution of frontier adopters to aggregate de-routinization reflects the inherent routine-replacing nature of frontier technologies (within firms effect), results from unequal access to adopting these technologies (between adoption groups effect), or depends on specific conditions within adopting firms (within adoption groups effect) has very different policy implications. To quantify the relative contribution of each channel, we perform a decomposition analysis in the next section.

3.3 Decomposing aggregate de-routinization

In order to decompose aggregate de-routinization, we build on Autor et al. (2020) and Acemoglu et al. (2020) and decompose aggregate occupational employment shifts into those that occur *within firms*, between firms and *between adoption groups*, and between firms but *within adoption groups*.²⁴ In particular, we decompose the change in the aggregate employment share (e.g., routine jobs), $\Delta\lambda$, as follows:

$$\Delta\lambda = \underbrace{\sum_g \Delta\bar{\lambda}_g}_{\text{within firms}} + \underbrace{\sum_g \Delta(\bar{\lambda}_g - \bar{\lambda}) \left(\tilde{s}_g - \frac{G}{F}\right)}_{\text{between adoption groups}} + \underbrace{\sum_g \Delta \sum_{f \in g} (\lambda_f - \bar{\lambda}_g) \left(\tilde{s}_f - \frac{w_f}{F}\right)}_{\text{within adoption groups}} \quad (4)$$

²⁴This approach differs from classic within-between decompositions such as, e.g., Harrigan et al. (2021). In particular, we decompose aggregate changes by adopter groups and further differentiate between-firm shifts into those that take place within adopter groups from those occurring between adopter groups. Our within-firms component is free of any firm-size related weights and therefore represents an average within-firm shift unrelated to firm size. We build on Autor et al. (2020) and Acemoglu et al. (2020), who focus on shifts in labor shares. We generalize their approach to more than two groups, introduce sampling weights to account for the firm survey design, and decompose residual changes in the covariance term.

where λ is the aggregate employment share of an occupation, $\Delta\lambda$ is its change over time, $\bar{\lambda}_g$ is the average firm-weighted share of an occupation in adopter group g , $\bar{\lambda}$ is the average firm-weighted share of an occupation in the aggregate economy, \tilde{s}_g is the share of adopter group g in total employment, G and F are the weighted total number of firms of adopter group g and across all groups, respectively, λ_f is the share of an occupation in firm f , \tilde{s}_f is the employment share of firm f , and w_f is the survey weight of firm f .²⁵ The *first* component of equation (4) captures the average occupation change within firms over time by adopter group, $\bar{\lambda}_g$, for $g \in \{non; digital; frontier\}$. The *second* component captures changes in deviations of the group-specific mean from the average employment change in the economy, $\bar{\lambda}$. To restore representativeness regarding total employment, this term is weighted by deviations between the group-specific employment share, \tilde{s}_g , and the relative number of firms of each adopter group (G/F). The *third* component captures deviations in firms' occupation change from the group-specific mean. This term is again weighted by the deviations of firms' employment shares, \tilde{s}_f , from firms' relative survey weight (w_f/F). Each component of equation (4) is calculated for each adopter group. Summing each component over the three adopter groups and adding up the three components yields the total aggregate occupation change in the economy.²⁶ The details of the decomposition are shown in Appendix C.

Based on equation (4), we conduct the decomposition for each adopter group and construct confidence bands based on jackknife standard errors. In the following discussion, we focus on the results for the group of frontier adopters, which experience the fastest de-routinization among their workforce. Additional, mostly insignificant results for digital adopters and non-adopters can be found in Appendix D. Moreover, Appendix E shows that our decomposition analysis is robust to alternative sample choices, alternative classifications of firms into adoption status, and an alternative classification of occupations by main task type based on the O*Net database.

Decomposing how frontier technology adopters contribute to de-routinization. Figure 2 presents the contribution of frontier technology adopters to de-routinization in the economy and the decomposition into the three components of equation (4). It shows that the contribution to the overall decline in routine jobs by frontier adopters is not driven by within firms effects (first component in equation 4). In fact, the average frontier adopter (insignificantly) increases

²⁵ \tilde{s}_g and \tilde{s}_f take account of firms' survey weights when computing employment shares.

²⁶Appendix Figure D.5 panel (a) displays the contribution of each adoption group g to aggregate occupational shifts shown in Figure 1 panel (b). Appendix Figure D.5 panel (b) displays the contribution of each component of equation 4 to aggregate occupational shifts.

rather than decreases the share of routine jobs at the firm level. Hence, the contribution of frontier technology adopters to overall de-routinization is not a simple story of new technologies generally substituting for routine jobs within adopting firms, but must be driven by between-firm shifts. This result is in line with Harrigan et al. (2021) who document that the aggregate rise of technology-related occupations in France between 1994 and 2007 is not driven by within-firm adjustments but by changes in the composition between firms.

Figure 2: Frontier technology adopters' contribution to de-routinization between 2011 and 2016

Notes: The figure displays frontier technology adopters' contribution to aggregate de-routinization between 2011 and 2016 and differentiated by the three components from equation 4: the contribution of the within firms, between adoption groups and within adoption group component. The total contribution (first bar) represents the contribution of frontier adopters to the aggregate de-routinization displayed in Figure 1 panel (a). Weighted with firm stratification weights. NRC: non-routine cognitive jobs; RC/RM: routine cognitive/manual jobs; NRM: non-routine manual jobs. Confidence bands based on jackknife standard errors.

Complementing this evidence, we further find that between firm shifts are not taking place between adoption groups. The between adoption groups component (second component in equation 4) turns out to be a negligible source of the contribution of frontier adopters to aggregate employment changes.²⁷

Instead, the contribution of frontier technology adopters to aggregate de-routinization is explained by differences between firms within the group of frontier adopters, i.e., the within adoption groups component (third component in equation 4). Accordingly, heterogeneity between firms *within* the group of frontier adopters explains the contribution of frontier adopters to

²⁷The irrelevance of the between adoption group component aligns with three key empirical observations, as discussed in detail in Appendix D.

aggregate de-routinization. Put differently, only a subset of firms with specific initial conditions contribute to de-routinization. We next aim to better understand this heterogeneity by further decomposing the within-group component.²⁸

Zooming into the within adoption groups effect. Figure 3 further decomposes the within adoption groups effect into a scale, composition, and simultaneous effect. The scale effect reflects differences in occupational employment changes by firms that differ in initial firm size. The composition effect reflects differences in firm growth between firms that differ in initial occupational composition, and the simultaneous effect captures the combination of the two.²⁹

Figure 3: Sources of the within adoption groups effect for frontier technology adopters

Notes: The figure displays the decomposition of the within adoption groups effect for frontier adopters as shown in Appendix equation (13): contribution of frontier adopters to aggregate de-routinization between 2011 and 2016 due to occupational employment shifts induced between frontier adopting firms related to size, composition differences, and a combination of both. Scale, composition and simultaneous components add up to the total within adoption groups effect of frontier adopters. The total within adoption groups effect for frontier adopters (first bar) corresponds to the within groups component (dark blue shaded bar) displayed in Figure 2. NRC: non-routine cognitive jobs; RC/RM: routine cognitive/manual jobs; NRM: non-routine manual jobs. Confidence bands based on jackknife standard errors.

Figure 3 highlights that both, scale and composition effects play a sizeable role in the decline in routine jobs and the rise of non-routine cognitive jobs, while the simultaneous effect is

²⁸Appendix D documents that digital technology adopters contribute to the aggregate de-routinization by shifts within firms and shifts between firms within the group of digital adopters, both components are equally in magnitude but statistically insignificant. These results are in line with Böckerman et al. (2019) documenting that firm-level ICT usage leads to de-routinization within adopting firms. Also note the absence of any significant sub-components of the within adoption groups component for digital adopters. For non-adopters, neither the overall contribution to de-routinization is significant, nor any of the sub-components.

²⁹The respective decomposition formula and some further explanation can be found in equation (13) in Appendix C.

negligible.³⁰ Hence, the aggregate decline in the routine employment share among the workers employed at frontier adopters occurs because (1) initially larger frontier adopters reduce their routine employment share in contrast to smaller frontier adopters (scale effect) and because (2) initially less routine-intensive firms experience stronger employment growth (composition effect).

Taken together, the findings from the decomposition suggest that the adoption of frontier technology does not lead to a widespread replacement of routine jobs within firms. Rather, only a subset of larger firms is responsible for the de-routinization among frontier adopters. At the same time, firms that already have a higher share of non-routine cognitive jobs are in a better position to benefit from technology adoption and thus grow faster. In the next section, we investigate the source of the scale and composition effect to gain a better understanding of the underlying mechanisms.

4 Delving into the heterogeneity among frontier adopters

In this section, we aim to understand whether de-routinization among frontier adopters is driven by genuine scale and composition effects, or whether these effects rather reflect other factors that the decomposition framework does not incorporate. Understanding the sources of the scale and composition effects is key for deriving policy implications. For this, we turn to a regression approach to estimate the roles of initial occupational composition and firm size for de-routinization, while controlling for various potentially related firm characteristics.³¹

4.1 Scale effect among frontier adopters

While the decomposition revealed a size-related decline in routine jobs among frontier adopters (scale effect), these employment shifts might reflect other characteristics related to larger frontier adopters, such as the sector of activity, the firm's age, or a workforce composition favoring routine replacement. To explore the relevance of such characteristics, we regress changes in occupational employment shares on firm size and subsequently extend the set of control variables. If these additional factors eliminate the size effect, this gives us insights into potential mechanisms underlying the size effect. In particular, we estimate:

³⁰Appendix Figure D.1 shows the corresponding decomposition of the between adoption groups effect of frontier adopters into size, composition, and simultaneous effects. None of these effects are significant, which is in line with three key empirical observations, as discussed in detail in Appendix D.

³¹An alternative to the regression analysis would be a decomposition within more homogeneous subgroups. However, our sample size of 172 firms adopting frontier technologies makes such a further sample split infeasible.

$$\Delta\lambda_f = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=2}^4 \gamma_i S_{if} + \beta X_f + \epsilon_f \quad (5)$$

where $\Delta\lambda_f$ is the change in firm f 's employment share of a given occupation group, S_{if} is a set of firm-size dummies where firms with fewer than 10 workers are the reference category, and X_f is a set of further controls that potentially explain the heterogeneity across firms.

Table 3 shows the results.³² Consistent with the decomposition, regressing the change in RC/RM jobs on firm size without further controls confirms the scale effect, i.e., significant negative estimates increasing in magnitude for the firm-size dummies (column 1). However, this scale effect might be driven by size-related heterogeneity in core firm characteristics such as sector of activity, firm age, or general firm performance.³³ Yet, controlling for these characteristics in column 2 does not weaken, but rather strengthens the scale effect. The change in routine employment is 12.9 percentage points lower for large firms compared to small firms, which is sizable compared to the average shift of 1.85 percentage points.

The scale effect might also reflect size-related differences in the initial workforce composition. For instance, larger firms might have initially higher shares of routine workers and, therefore, experience stronger routine-replacing effects. Adding initial employment shares across the main task type (3 categories), skill shares (4 categories), age shares (3 categories), and the share of IT workers in column 3, however, does not reduce the scale effect. Thus, the firm's initial workforce structure does not contribute to the observed size-related heterogeneity in the task shifts among frontier adopters.

Another size-related source of heterogeneity might stem from capital investments. Although all firms in our regression analysis are frontier adopters, there might be heterogeneity in the initial technology-specific capital stock in 2011 or technology-specific investments between 2011 and 2016. For example, larger firms may already have been better equipped with frontier technologies in 2011 or may have invested more in frontier technologies since 2011 than smaller frontier adopters. Yet, column 4 speaks against this hypothesis. Thus, initial technology use and even the quantity of investments also do not explain the size-related heterogeneity in task shifts among frontier adopters.³⁴

³²Note that Table 3 displays the result for the change in RC/RM employment since the NRC results are almost a mirror image of the RC/RM decline and changes in RC/RM, NRC and NRM employment add up to zero.

³³We capture firm performance by the percentile in which the firm belongs across the wage premia, estimated by firm fixed effects based on the approach proposed by Abowd et al. (1999).

³⁴The size effect does also not diminish when controlling for firm differences in churning and turnover rates (pre-2011) as an indicator of a firm's ability to quickly restructure its workforce, or in entry wages as an indicator

Table 3: Decline in routine employment of frontier adopters between 2011 and 2016

Dependent variable: Change in firm-level employment share of routine jobs ($\Delta RC/RM$)							
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
Firm size (reference: <10 employees):							
10-49 employees	-0.011 (0.037)	-0.081* (0.048)	-0.111 (0.067)	-0.070 (0.061)	-0.042 (0.045)	-0.060 (0.050)	-0.007 (0.042)
50-199 employees	-0.049** (0.019)	-0.131*** (0.031)	-0.158*** (0.044)	-0.137** (0.054)	-0.009 (0.047)	-0.073 (0.056)	0.004 (0.058)
200+ employees	-0.058*** (0.018)	-0.129*** (0.028)	-0.145*** (0.042)	-0.192*** (0.055)	-0.098* (0.052)	-0.115 (0.071)	-0.062 (0.072)
Adj R^2	0.004	0.094	0.160	0.290	0.591	0.447	0.536
Firm characteristics		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Workforce structure			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Capital structure				✓	✓	✓	✓
Perceptions					✓		
Skill demands						✓	✓
Training							✓

Notes: $N = 172$. The average firm-weighted shift in routine jobs among the 172 frontier adopters is +1.85pp (note that this corresponds to the respective figure in Figure 2 divided by 0.079 which is the share of frontier adopters among all firms, see Table 2). The set of firm characteristics include a dummy for the self-assessment of whether the firm should be considered as a manufacturer or service provider, sector (5 categories), firm age (dummy if founded after 2001), firm performance (AKM fixed effects). The workforce structure characteristics refer to the initial values in 2011 and include initial employment shares across main task types (3 categories), skill shares (4 categories), age shares (3 categories), and the share of IT workers. The capital structure characteristics include the initial level of technology-specific capital stocks and the change in the technology-specific capital stocks between 2011 and 2016. Perceptions include the assessment of chances and risks related to the adoption of frontier technologies (16 dimensions), see Appendix Table F.1. Skill demands include the assessment of how skill demands changed in the past five years (14 dimensions), see Appendix Table F.2. Training includes a set of variables describing how the extent and content of vocational and further training changed in the past five years (10 dimensions), see Appendix Table F.3.

One remaining explanation for the scale effect might be that firm size affects the type of frontier technology that is implemented or the way how such technologies are implemented. To get tentative evidence on the role of such factors, column 5 adds subjective perceptions from the survey about the chances and risks associated with the use of frontier technologies. In total, we asked the interviewees to assess how they perceive potential chances and risks of adopting frontier technologies. The 16 items include potential risks such as high investment costs, restructuring needs, and labor shortages, but also potential benefits such as labor cost savings. See Appendix F for more information about all 16 perception dimensions.³⁵ Column 5 of Table 3 shows that the

of the firm's ability to hire new NRC workers.

³⁵Note that firms were asked a random subset of perceptions in the survey. We impute the randomly missing items as described in Appendix F and display the random forest classification results in Appendix Table F.1. Using the original items and a missing indicator for randomly missing items provides comparable results. As a drawback of the randomization, it is infeasible to isolate the marginal effect of each perception measure. Hence, we only discuss their joint effects.

inclusion of these perceptions substantially lowers the coefficient on the firm-size dummies and eliminates statistical significance except for the largest group of firms.

The results so far tentatively indicate that the size heterogeneity in occupational employment shifts partially reflects that larger firms differ in why they invest in frontier technologies and how they think about implementing them. One particular aspect of implementing frontier technologies could be the adjustment to changing skill requirements. If larger firms invest in frontier technologies that change skill requirements more profoundly, this may necessitate stronger adjustments of the workforce to changing skill demands. To test this channel, column (6) alternatively adds indicators from the survey about how firms view changing skill requirements during the last five years with respect to 14 skill dimensions.³⁶ This results in a large drop of coefficients compared to column 4 and entirely eliminates the statistical significance of the size effects.

Changing skill requirements should be accompanied by changing training needs. Adding survey information on how firms assess how vocational and further training needs and content changed between 2011 and 2016 in column 7, further reduces the coefficient sizes for the size dummies.³⁷

Overall, these results highlight that the scale effect is remarkably stable to a large set of controls as it cannot be explained by any initial differences in firm workforce characteristics or by prior investments in frontier technologies. Our findings tentatively suggest that the size heterogeneity reflects differences in which frontier technologies get adopted and how they get implemented. The heterogeneity between large and small frontier adopters in implementing frontier technologies is also reflected in how they perceive changes in skill requirements and training needs. Hence, the adoption of frontier technologies in larger firms boosts de-routinization compared to smaller firms.

³⁶See Appendix F for more information about the 14 skill dimensions. Note that firms were asked a random subset of skill demands in the survey. We impute the randomly missing items by means of a random forest classification and display the results in Appendix Table F.2. Using the original items and a missing indicator for randomly missing items provides comparable results.

³⁷See Appendix F for more information about the ten items on how vocational training and further training changed in the past five years. We impute missing items by means of a random forest classification and display the results in Appendix Table F.3. Using the original items and a missing indicator for missing items provides comparable results.

4.2 Composition effect among frontier adopters

We follow a similar approach to shed light on why frontier adopters with an initially high share of NRC employment (low share of RC/RM employment) grow faster compared to the average frontier adopter. For this, we regress firms' employment growth on firms' initial occupational employment shares and subsequently extend the set of control variables:

$$\Delta \log N_f = \beta_0 + \gamma_i \lambda_{if} + \beta X_f + \epsilon_f \quad (6)$$

where $\Delta \log N_f$ gives the log employment growth between 2011 and 2016 and λ_{if} gives the initial firm-level share of a given occupation group $i \in \{NRC; RC/RM; NRM\}$ for firm f with routine jobs being the reference category.

Table 4 shows the results. Without any further controls, column 1 confirms the significantly positive correlation between the share of NRC employment and firm employment growth from the decomposition. Adding firm characteristics related to the sector of activity, firm age, and firm performance in column 2, does not weaken this positive growth effect, i.e., these characteristics do not explain why a high initial NRC share results in stronger employment growth among frontier adopters. This growth effect also remains stable when adding the firm's workforce structure in terms of age and IT personnel in column 3.³⁸ In column 4, we test whether composition-related heterogeneity stems from differences in the capital structure with respect to the initial capital stock or technology-specific investments between 2011 and 2016. Yet, column 4 shows that adding these indicators does not affect the strength or direction of the NRC effect.

Contrary to the scale effect in the previous subsection, neither adding the perceived chances and risks of frontier technology adoption (column 5), the changing skill demands (column 6), nor adding the changes in vocational and further training needs (column 7) mitigate the composition effect.³⁹ In fact, the growth-enhancing effect of an initially high NRC-intensive workforce becomes slightly stronger when adding these controls.⁴⁰ Hence, firms with an initially higher

³⁸We leave out the skill composition as this is highly correlated with the task composition. In fact, when using the skill group shares rather than the task shares, we find that firms with a higher initial share of specialists tend to grow faster. Hence, we could look at skill shifts rather than task shifts and find a complementary story of higher skills being beneficial for a firm's ability to grow when adopting frontier technologies.

³⁹Note that firms were asked a random subset of these three covariates and we impute the randomly missing items as described in Appendix F. Using the original items and a missing indicator for randomly missing items provides comparable results.

⁴⁰The increase in the magnitude of the growth-enhancing effect of an initially high NRC-intensive workforce in columns 5-7 also tentatively suggests a negative omitted variable bias in columns 1-4. This likely arises because firms with an initially high share of NRC workers select into more complex frontier technologies with greater skill demands and training needs, and the adoption of these complex technologies slows down firms' growth potential.

Table 4: Employment growth of frontier adopters between 2011 and 2016

Dependent variable: Change in firm-level employment ($\Delta \log N_f$)							
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
Initial occupational employment structure (reference: RC/RM jobs):							
NRC share	0.265*** (0.078)	0.229** (0.107)	0.234** (0.108)	0.274** (0.114)	0.348*** (0.119)	0.417*** (0.130)	0.357*** (0.136)
NRM share	-0.071 (0.161)	-0.034 (0.158)	0.027 (0.140)	0.095 (0.153)	0.112 (0.165)	0.189 (0.147)	0.228 (0.163)
Adj R^2	0.067	0.122	0.132	0.207	0.242	0.247	0.271
Firm characteristics		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Workforce structure			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Capital structure				✓	✓	✓	✓
Perceptions					✓		
Skill demands						✓	✓
Training							✓

Notes: $N = 172$. The average change in the dependent variable among the 172 frontier adopters is $\Delta \log N_f = 0.118$. The set of firm characteristics include a dummy for the self-assessment of whether the firm should be considered as a manufacturer or service provider, sector (5 categories), firm size (4 categories), firm age (dummy if founded after 2001), firm performance (AKM fixed effects). The workforce characteristics refer to the initial values in 2011 and include age shares (3 categories) and the share of IT workers. The capital structure characteristics include the initial level of technology-specific capital stocks (in logs) and the change in the technology-specific capital stocks (in logs) between 2011 and 2016. Perceptions include the assessment of chances and risks related to the adoption of frontier technologies (16 dimensions), see Appendix Table F.1. Skill demands include the assessment of how skill demands changed in the past five years (14 dimensions), see Appendix Table F.2. Training includes a set of variables describing how the extent and content of vocational and further training changed in the past five years (10 dimensions), see Appendix Table F.3.

NRC employment share are better prepared to benefit from the growth potential of a given set of frontier technologies, likely because the firm’s initial skill structure is more complementary to new frontier technologies from the start compared to a firm with initially low NRC employment share.

This exercise demonstrates that the composition effect is robust to adding a wide set of controls. Firms who are already specialized in complementary, non-routine cognitive jobs, grow faster. Firms’ NRC employment specialization therefore seems to play a crucial role in firms’ ability to benefit from the adoption of new frontier technologies.

5 Conclusion

Extensive literature demonstrates that computer-controlled machines have displaced workers in routine jobs (Acemoglu and Autor, 2011). The emergence of frontier technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI), augmented reality and cloud computing has sparked concerns about

the potential impact on a broader spectrum of jobs. However, due to the paucity of granular firm-level data on the adoption of frontier technologies, our understanding of the relationship between frontier technology adoption at the firm level and overall changes in the employment structure remains partial.

We add to this question by constructing a novel linked employer-employee dataset that captures firms' actual technology adoption for a representative sample of service and manufacturing firms that we link to German administrative employee records. Based on this unique data source, we are able to draw the most comprehensive picture to date on the role of firm-level adoption of frontier technologies for occupational shifts in the economy. For this, we distinguish between firms mainly adopting frontier technologies of the recent wave of technological change from those adopting more mature digital technologies that started to be introduced in the 1980s.

By means of a decomposition exercise and additional regressions, our study reveals three novel findings: First, we demonstrate that firms adopting frontier technologies significantly contribute to the overall decline in routine jobs and increase in non-routine cognitive jobs in Germany between 2011 and 2016. Hence, de-routinization in the aggregate economy continues with frontier technology adoption.

Second, despite this overall picture, there is no widespread replacement of routine jobs *within* firms adopting frontier technologies. The average frontier adopter even insignificantly increases its routine employment share. The contribution of frontier adopters to the economy-wide employment shift instead stems from a subset of frontier adopters: Large frontier adopters reduce their routine job shares and increase their non-routine cognitive employment share to a greater extent than smaller frontier adopters. At the same time, firms with initially high proportions of non-routine cognitive intensive workers experience stronger employment growth. Hence, drawing conclusions about the overall routine-replacing character of frontier technologies from average adjustments within firms adopting these technologies, as is often done in empirical studies, is subject to a fallacy that underestimates the economy-wide contribution of frontier adopters to de-routinization.

Third, we provide evidence that this fallacy arises from the varying preparedness of frontier adopters to successfully implement cutting-edge technologies. Frontier adopters with a non-routine cognitive intensive workforce experience significantly stronger employment growth which indicates enhanced productivity following the investment in frontier technologies. At the same time, the significant decline in routine jobs among large adopters of frontier technologies can be

attributed to firms' perceptions of changing skill demands and training needs. This highlights that larger firms are better able to invest in skills that complement frontier technologies.

Our paper thus also highlights a new source of inequality between firms adopting frontier technologies and emphasizes that policies that improve the availability of complementary skills have the potential to mitigate rising inequality across firms. Otherwise, the adoption of frontier technologies may exacerbate between-firm inequality and bolster market power for successful adopters of frontier technology. Moreover, while the role of complementary skills and complementary investments in the implementation of new technologies has also been stressed in much of the recent literature, our paper highlights its economy-wide implications as complementary skills also turn out to be a key driver of economy-wide de-routinization. The pace at which routine jobs decline would likely accelerate further if complementary skills became more widely available to firms, facilitating the shift towards non-routine cognitive jobs. Hence, future research should revisit aggregate employment changes as frontier technologies mature and examine the role of skill availability as a mediating factor.

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Online Appendix

Appendix A Additional tables

Table A.1: Average technology shares as reported in the firm survey

	All	non-adopters	digital adopters	frontier adopters
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
<i>Panel A: Share in 2011</i>				
manual tech	0.573	0.788	0.409	0.371
digital tech	0.376	0.196	0.545	0.348
frontier tech	0.051	0.017	0.046	0.281
<i>Panel B: Share in 2016</i>				
manual tech	0.500	0.776	0.284	0.262
digital tech	0.427	0.203	0.650	0.324
frontier tech	0.073	0.020	0.066	0.413

Notes: Table shows the subjective assessment of the survey respondent how the firm's equipment is distributed over the technology classes as defined in Table 1. The shares are weighted with firm stratification weights. Panel A presents the results for 2011. Panel B presents the results for 2016.

Table A.2: Technology use across sectors

	Manufacturing		Service	
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
<i>Panel A: Technology-specific capital stock in 2011 (in 1,000 € and in %)</i>				
manual tech	117.3	45.3%	63.8	47.4%
digital tech	125.1	48.3%	61.2	45.5%
frontier tech	16.5	6.4%	9.5	7.1%
<i>Panel B: Technology-specific capital stock in 2016 (in 1,000 € and in %)</i>				
manual tech	174.6	38.2%	99.5	38.4%
digital tech	231.4	50.7%	132.6	51.3%
frontier tech	50.7	11.1%	26.7	10.3%
<i>Panel C: Representing number of firms and workers</i>				
# firms (in K)	312.7		1612.4	
# workers (in M)	6.4		21.5	
Observations	583		1,077	

Notes: Table shows mean statistics weighted with firm stratification weights. Uneven columns give the capital stock in 1,000 € and even columns give the relative shares of the capital stocks across technology classes in % adding up to 100. Panel A presents the results for 2011. Panel B presents the results for 2016.

Table A.3: Initial firm and workforce characteristics by adoption group

	Non-adopters	digital adopters	frontier adopters
	(1)	(2)	(3)
<i>Panel A: Firm characteristics</i>			
Sector			
Secondary not know-int	0.456	0.160	0.090
Secondary know-int	0.017	0.025	0.008
Tertiary not know-int	0.404	0.481	0.363
Tertiary know-int	0.114	0.305	0.492
ICT sector	0.009	0.028	0.047
Manufacturing firm	0.244	0.108	0.038
Avg. firm employment (in heads)	10.5	17.4	19.1
Avg. firm daily wage (in €)	80.3	98.1	105.4
Firm Wage Premium	12.2	14.1	15.1
MDF port within reach	0.960	0.959	0.997
<i>Panel B: Workforce characteristics</i>			
Worker shares by main task of occupation			
NRC	0.238	0.329	0.358
RC/RM	0.399	0.449	0.491
NRM	0.362	0.222	0.151
Worker shares by required skill level			
Unskilled workers	0.139	0.100	0.119
Professionals	0.698	0.631	0.575
Specialists	0.088	0.130	0.136
Experts	0.075	0.139	0.170
Worker shares by age group			
<40 years of age	0.430	0.390	0.420
40-55 years of age	0.458	0.487	0.480
>55 years of age	0.112	0.123	0.100
Observations	525	963	172

Notes: The tables displays averages among firms across adoption groups for the initial observation period 2011 based on the entire sample of 1,660 firms. Statistics in Panel A are weighted with firm stratification weights. Appendix Table B.1 defines the five sector aggregates. The variable manufacturing firm stems from a self-assessment during the firm survey of whether the firm should be considered as a manufacturer or service provider. The firm wage premium corresponds to firm fixed effects for the period 2003-2010 based on the method by Abowd et al. (1999). These AKM FE are only available for 1,536 firms. Panel B represents the share of workers employed in each category and statistics are weighted by employment-weighted firm stratification weights. NRC: non-routine cognitive jobs; RC/RM: Routine cognitive/manual jobs; NRM: non-routine manual jobs.

Appendix B Data

Sector definition

To group firms along their business activities into sector aggregates, we follow the basic division along the primary (agriculture, fishing, or mining), secondary (manufacturing or construction), and tertiary sectors (trade, banking, education, or health services). Given that the primary sector only employs a minor share of total employment (about 1.5%), we focus on the distinction between the secondary and tertiary sectors. Instead, we further distinguish between knowledge-intensive and not knowledge-intensive sectors within the secondary and tertiary sectors and identify the ICT sector (information technology services or telecommunication services) separately. Firms in the primary sector are assigned to the not knowledge-intensive manufacturing sector.

Table B.1: Definition of sectors

Sector aggregates	German classification of economic activities
Secondary Sector	
Not knowledge-intensive manufacturing	11-99, 101-182, 221-259, 310-439
Knowledge-intensive manufacturing	191-212, 265-267, 271-309
Tertiary Sector	
Not knowledge-intensive service	451-464, 466-563, 681-683, 771-856, 871-889, 920-949, 952-990
Knowledge-intensive service	581, 591-602, 639-663, 691-750, 861-869, 900-910
ICT Sector	261-264, 268, 465, 582, 611-631, 951

Notes: The corresponding time-consistent three-digit codes of the German Classification of Economic Activities 2008 (WZ 2008) correspond to the NACE Rev. 2 industry codes.

Capital stock imputation

Although the IAB-ZEW-Labor Market 4.0-Establishment Survey (BIZA) includes rich information on firms' equipment by level of technological advancement, it misses information on the absolute value of the capital stock. Since the survey was conducted as a CATI, we considered it infeasible to ask for the technology-specific capital stocks across time during the interview. We adopt the procedure proposed by Janser et al. (2023) to impute capital stock information for the firms in our sample. The procedure consists of two steps.

In the first step, Janser et al. (2023) compute establishment-specific capital stocks using the investment data in the IAB Establishment Panel based on the perpetual inventory method. The IAB Establishment Panel is an annual representative survey on various topics including determinants of labor demand, investment activity, and workforce characteristics. The basis for the sampling of the IAB Establishment Panel comprises the universe of all German establishments

with at least one employee subject to social insurance contributions as of the reference date 30 June of the previous year Bechmann et al. (2021). The procedure proposed by Janser et al. (2023) relies on the investment information from the IAB Establishment Panel for conducting a perpetual inventory approach building on Berlemann and Wesselhöft (2014). The approach comprises several methods to remove outliers and control for business cycle fluctuations.

In the second step, Janser et al. (2023) merge these firms with additional administrative information that is available for the universe of firms and train a statistical learning model to predict capital stocks based on information that is available for all firms in Germany. The administrative information stems from the IAB Establishment History Panel.⁴¹ The statistical learning method is divided into one model for firms' capital stock levels and one for changes in firms' capital stocks. The trained statistical learning models are used to predict capital stocks per year for all our survey establishments. As predictors for the capital stock K_{jt} for establishment j and year $t = 2011, \dots, 2016$ several characteristics are used such as establishment size, age, sector affiliation, location, and employment structure.

It can be shown that these imputed capital stocks closely predict external capital stock information for a subset of firms for which direct information on firms' capital stocks (i.e., fixed assets) is available. We use these predicted capital stocks per year for the survey establishments in our sample to assign each establishment a yearly overall capital stock K_{ft} . We compute technology-specific capital stocks \bar{K}_{fgt} by multiplying the overall capital stock K_{ft} with the shares of firms' work equipment by technology level k_{fgt} .

Technology adoption definition

To classify firms into three adopter groups $g \in (\textit{non}; \textit{digital}; \textit{frontier})$ according to their technology investments, we proceed in two steps: First, we classify a firm f as a g -adopter if it predominantly increases its g -technology capital stock relative to the other technology capital stocks:

$$g\text{-adopter} \Leftarrow \max(\Delta \bar{K}_{f,g=\textit{manual}}, \Delta \bar{K}_{f,g=\textit{digital}}, \Delta \bar{K}_{f,g=\textit{frontier}}) \quad (7)$$

where $g \in (\textit{manual}; \textit{digital}; \textit{frontier})$ indexes the level of technological advancement and $\Delta \bar{K}_{f,g}$ defines the change in the technology-specific capital stocks between 2011 and 2016

⁴¹See Ganzer et al. (2021) for more details about the BHP. Access to the BHP is provided by the Research Data Center (FDZ) of the German Federal Employment Agency at the IAB (see <http://fdz.iab.de>).

$$K_{fg}^{t=2016} - K_{fg}^{t=2011}.$$

In particular:

$$g\text{-adopter} = \begin{cases} \textit{frontier} & \text{if } \Delta K_{\textit{frontier}} \geq \Delta K_{f,\textit{manual}} \wedge \Delta K_{\textit{frontier}} \geq \Delta K_{\textit{digital}} \wedge \Delta K_{\textit{frontier}} \neq 0 \wedge k_{\textit{frontier},t_{16}} \neq 0 \\ \textit{digital} & \text{if } \Delta K_{\textit{digital}} > \Delta K_{\textit{manual}} \wedge \Delta K_{\textit{digital}} > \Delta K_{\textit{frontier}} \wedge \Delta K_{\textit{digital}} \neq 0 \wedge k_{\textit{digital},t_{16}} \neq 0 \\ \textit{non} & \text{if } \Delta K_{\textit{manual}} \geq \Delta K_{\textit{digital}} \wedge \Delta K_{\textit{manual}} > \Delta K_{\textit{frontier}} \wedge \Delta K_{\textit{manual}} \neq 0 \wedge k_{\textit{manual},t_{16}} \neq 0 \end{cases}$$

This step assigns all but two survey firms (after our selection steps) to one of the three adoption groups.

Second, if one of the other technology-specific capital shares is zero, the g -adoption status is defined as follows:

$$g\text{-adopter} = \begin{cases} \textit{frontier} & \text{if } k_{\textit{frontier},t_{16}} \neq 0 \wedge k_{\textit{digital},t_{16}} \neq 0 \wedge k_{\textit{manual},t_{16}} = 0 \wedge \Delta K_{\textit{frontier}} > \Delta K_{\textit{digital}} \\ \textit{frontier} & \text{if } k_{\textit{frontier},t_{16}} \neq 0 \wedge k_{\textit{manual},t_{16}} \neq 0 \wedge k_{\textit{digital},t_{16}} = 0 \wedge \Delta K_{\textit{frontier}} > \Delta K_{\textit{manual}} \\ \textit{digital} & \text{if } k_{\textit{digital},t_{16}} \neq 0 \wedge k_{\textit{manual},t_{16}} \neq 0 \wedge k_{\textit{frontier},t_{16}} = 0 \wedge \Delta K_{\textit{digital}} > \Delta K_{\textit{manual}} \\ \textit{digital} & \text{if } k_{\textit{digital},t_{16}} \neq 0 \wedge k_{\textit{frontier},t_{16}} \neq 0 \wedge k_{\textit{manual},t_{16}} = 0 \wedge \Delta K_{\textit{digital}} > \Delta K_{\textit{frontier}} \\ \textit{non} & \text{if } k_{\textit{manual},t_{16}} \neq 0 \wedge k_{\textit{digital},t_{16}} \neq 0 \wedge k_{\textit{frontier},t_{16}} = 0 \wedge \Delta K_{\textit{manual}} > \Delta K_{\textit{digital}} \\ \textit{non} & \text{if } k_{\textit{manual},t_{16}} \neq 0 \wedge k_{\textit{frontier},t_{16}} \neq 0 \wedge k_{\textit{digital},t_{16}} = 0 \wedge \Delta K_{\textit{manual}} > \Delta K_{\textit{frontier}} \end{cases}$$

This step assigns an adoption status to the remaining 2 survey firms.

Difference to a capital-shares approach. Our approach defined above relies on the use of imputed technology-specific capital stocks K_{fgt} . Alternatively, one could rely on changes in the reported technology shares k_{fgt} . The former approach has the disadvantage of requiring imputed capital stocks, while its main advantage is that it accounts for the net investments and yields a more stringent classification of frontier adopters. The latter approach has the disadvantage of not taking into account the level of capital stocks and its main advantage is to not require additional assumptions related to the capital stock imputation. In the following, we describe the differences between the two approaches in detail.

Consider two firms A and B which raise their shares of frontier and digital technologies both by 1 percentage point at the expense of older manual technologies. Suppose both firms initially rely on digital and frontier technologies to the same extent $k_{f,g=\textit{digital},t=0} = k_{f,g=\textit{frontier},t=0}$. In this case, both approaches would assign firm A and B to the group of frontier adopters. Suppose the initial shares of digital technologies exceeded the share of frontier technologies for firm B $k_{f=B,g=\textit{digital},t=0} > k_{f=B,g=\textit{frontier},t=0}$, while firm A still uses digital and frontier

technologies to the same extent in the initial year $k_{f=A,g=digital,t=0} = k_{f=A,g=frontier,t=0}$. In this case, the net investments into digital technologies exceed the net investments into frontier technologies for firm B $I_{f=B,g=digital} > I_{f=B,g=frontier}$, while they are equally large for firm A $I_{f=A,g=digital} = I_{f=A,g=frontier}$. In this case, the capital stock approach assigns firm B as a digital adopter, while the technology share approach assigns firm B as a frontier adopter.

More formally, the relationship between both approaches can be expressed as follows:

$$\Delta K_{fg} = K_{f,t=0}\Delta k_{fg} + k_{fg,t=0}\Delta K_f + \Delta K_f\Delta k_{fg} \quad (8)$$

where $K_{f,t=0}$ is the total capital stock across all technology types, $k_{fg,t=0}$ is the g -specific technology share for firm f in the initial period $t = 0$. Δ refers to the difference between 2011 and 2016. If the initial technology shares were the same across all technology types ($k_{fg,t=0} = k_{fg',t=0}$), the technology type with the largest increase in the share would also be the technology type with the largest increase in the capital stock. Frontier technologies typically have a much smaller share initially (see Table 2). Thus, focusing on changes in technology shares Δk_{fg} results in a more lenient classification of frontier adopters: small changes in frontier technology shares are sufficient to classify a firm as a frontier adopter. Focusing on changes in technology-specific capital stocks ΔK_{fg} additionally emphasizes firms' net investments, yielding a more stringent classification of frontier adopters and thus differentiating potential differences between digital and frontier investments more precisely, avoiding a bias towards zero. In addition, de-investments in older manual technologies might appear as investments in frontier technologies by focusing exclusively on changes in the technology shares. Therefore, we focus on changes in technology-specific capital stocks ΔK_{fg} instead of changes in the technology shares Δk_{fg} .

In Appendix E, we use the approach focusing on the reported technology shares k_{fgt} to replicate the main results of our paper and report in Appendix Table E.1 a comparison of the assignment of firms into the three adoption groups between both approaches.

Determinants of firms' technology adoption

In this appendix, we discuss the determinants of firms' technology choice. Our novel measure of firm-level technology adoption allows differentiating between computer-controlled digital technologies and frontier technologies and our survey covers firms from both manufacturing and service industries. Therefore, we are the first to provide insights on factors underlying a firm's

decision to invest in *frontier* rather than computer-controlled digital technologies. For this, we investigate which firm-specific initial period characteristics influence this important decision margin by estimating the following regression specification:

$$P(g\text{-adopter}) = \alpha + \beta X_{f,t=2011} + \epsilon_f \quad (9)$$

where $P(g\text{-adopter})$ denotes either the probability of a firm f to mainly adopt any type of modern technology $g \in (\textit{digital}; \textit{frontier})$ (Table B.2, columns 1-3) or the probability of a firm to mainly adopt frontier rather than computer-controlled digital technologies (Table B.2, columns 4-6) and $X_{f,t=2011}$ is a set of initial-period firm and workforce characteristics which we choose based on the main potential forces behind a firm’s decision to invest in modern technologies in line with the existing theoretical and empirical literature. To estimate the probability to mainly adopt any type of modern technologies $g \in (\textit{digital}; \textit{frontier})$, we use as a dependent variable in columns 1-3 an indicator that is unity if a firm is either a digital or frontier adopter and zero otherwise. In columns 4-6, we exclude non-adopting firms and use an indicator as the dependent variable which is unity if firm f is a frontier adopter and zero for digital adopters.⁴² In the determinant analysis of technology adoption, we also use data on firms’ access to high-speed internet. For this, we use the kilometer distance of the firm to the next main distribution frame (MDF). In Germany, the so-called “last mile” between the firm location and the MDF typically relies on copper wires, which leads to reductions in internet speed with distance, as highlighted by Falck et al. (2014, 2021). While these studies used the distances between the centroids of all municipalities to the next MDF, we measure the exact distance between the establishment location and the closest MDF.

Starting with modern technology adoption in either digital or frontier technologies, columns 1-3 in Table B.2 document that manufacturing firms are about 25 percentage points less likely to adopt new technology than service firms. This highlights the importance of including service industries in the scope of the analysis when examining the adoption of new technology. Technology adopting firms in our sample are ex-ante larger than non-adopters (column 1), which is in line with previous studies documenting that firms adopting modern technologies are larger since firm size facilitates the amortization of investments (Koch et al., 2021; Bonfiglioli et al., 2020;

⁴²Note that by estimating the investment decision this way, we assume independence of irrelevant alternatives between the three adoption choices. Relaxing this assumption by estimating a multinomial probit, yields qualitatively similar results, see Appendix Table B.3. Hence, we prefer the simpler specification.

Table B.2: Determinants of firm-level technology adoption

	Adopting any modern technology			Adopting frontier technology		
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Manufacturing firm	-0.261*** (0.063)	-0.252*** (0.063)	-0.261*** (0.063)	-0.087* (0.046)	-0.070* (0.042)	-0.077* (0.043)
Firm wage premium		0.003 (0.005)	0.000 (0.005)		-0.003 (0.003)	-0.004 (0.003)
Firm employment	0.040** (0.016)		0.044** (0.018)	-0.017 (0.017)		0.014 (0.016)
MDF port within reach	-0.078 (0.095)	-0.072 (0.095)	-0.084 (0.095)	0.138** (0.058)	0.134** (0.061)	0.130** (0.061)
Worker shares by main task of occupation (reference: NRM)						
NRC	0.267*** (0.092)	0.253*** (0.093)	0.262*** (0.092)	0.133 (0.085)	0.127 (0.085)	0.133 (0.085)
RC/RM	0.311*** (0.072)	0.292*** (0.073)	0.308*** (0.072)	0.061 (0.073)	0.050 (0.069)	0.059 (0.071)
Worker shares by required skill level (reference: Professionals)						
Experts	0.330*** (0.107)	0.340*** (0.106)	0.328*** (0.108)	-0.035 (0.120)	-0.043 (0.111)	-0.043 (0.111)
Specialists	0.223** (0.104)	0.231** (0.106)	0.231** (0.107)	0.020 (0.121)	0.098 (0.115)	0.103 (0.115)
Unskilled workers	-0.194 (0.127)	-0.187 (0.125)	-0.198 (0.127)	0.282 (0.200)	0.242 (0.188)	0.234 (0.191)
Worker shares by age group (reference: 40-55 years of age)						
<40 years of age	-0.123 (0.087)	-0.124 (0.088)	-0.114 (0.088)	-0.169* (0.096)	-0.141 (0.089)	-0.142 (0.089)
>55 years of age	0.106 (0.149)	0.118 (0.146)	0.122 (0.152)	-0.323** (0.132)	-0.199* (0.109)	-0.193* (0.112)
Constant	0.399*** (0.117)	0.437*** (0.125)	0.381*** (0.125)	0.061 (0.083)	0.003 (0.077)	-0.016 (0.083)
Observations	1,660	1,660	1,660	1,135	1,135	1,135
R-squared	0.155	0.147	0.155	0.082	0.119	0.120

Notes: Columns 1-3 are based on the entire firm sample, while columns 4-6 are restricted to adopting firms. All models are estimated with firm stratification weights. The variable manufacturing firm stems from a self-assessment during the firm survey of whether the firm should be considered as a manufacturer or service provider. Firm employment enters in logarithmic form. Firm wage premium corresponds to firm fixed effects for the period 2003-2010 based on the method by Abowd et al. (1999). Includes dummy for missing high-speed internet access information (10 firms) and mostly small firms with missing firm wage premium (124 firms). NRC: non-routine cognitive jobs; RC/RM: routine cognitive/manual jobs; NRM: non-routine manual jobs. Robust standard errors in parentheses. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$.

Acemoglu et al., 2020; Zolas et al., 2020).⁴³ With respect to the workforce composition, we find that firms' share of routine workers positively correlates with the probability of adopting any modern technology (columns 1-3). This aligns with the finding of Koch et al. (2021) that

⁴³Similarly, Zolas et al. (2020) rely on a large-scale firm survey in the U.S. and find that AI adoption is rare and generally skewed towards larger firms. Equally, Acemoglu et al. (2022a) find for the U.S. that the adoption of AI, robotics, dedicated equipment, specialized software, and cloud computing remains low (especially for AI and robotics), varies substantially across industries, and concentrates on large and young firms.

firms with a high share of production tasks are more likely to adopt robots as they may have incentives to use this technology to replace these tasks. More generally, previous literature has shown that modern automation technologies substitute for routine jobs that follow well-defined rules (among others, e.g., Acemoglu and Autor, 2011; Acemoglu and Restrepo, 2018). Thus, the positive correlation between the initial share of routine workers and the propensity to adopt modern technology we find in Table B.2 might point to the potential labor-capital substitution potential in adopting firms. Additionally, the positive correlations between the employment share of experts and specialists and the probability of a firm adopting any type of modern technology (columns 1-3), suggest that firms also need skills that are complementary to implementing and maintaining modern technologies. The positive correlation between the share of NRC jobs and the probability of adopting modern technology additionally supports this hypothesis. This is in line with previous research findings that firms need high-skilled employees conducting non-routine analytical tasks to plan, implement, and maintain modern technologies (Harrigan et al., 2021, 2024; Bresnahan et al., 2002).

The decision to adopt the most recent frontier technologies rather than computer-controlled digital technologies (columns 4-6) shows only a few significant correlates. In particular, manufacturing firms and firms with a high share of older workers are less likely to mainly adopt frontier technologies. This finding is in line with studies showing a negative relationship between firms' workforce age and the probability of technology or software adoption (Meyer, 2011). The availability of a high-speed internet access point turns out to be the single most important correlate for the decision to mainly invest in frontier technologies.⁴⁴ Since frontier technologies connect physical and digital spheres to perform work processes automatically without human intervention, these technologies are fully integrated into the firms' central IT systems and require high-speed internet. This insight complements previous studies emphasizing the role of firm's ICT infrastructure for technology adoption, highlighting that the diffusion of high-speed broadband internet correlates positively with the adoption of computers (DeStefano et al., 2018; Nicoletti et al., 2020). Thus, the decision to adopt frontier rather than digital technologies significantly relates to conducive conditions such as a favorable age structure and high-speed internet access,

⁴⁴We control for the availability of high-speed internet by including an indicator of whether a firm's location is within the reach of a high-speed internet access point. Beyond these access points, internet speed deteriorates markedly. Falck et al. (2014) show that the roll-out of the first generation of digital subscriber line (DSL) technology in Germany was entirely built on the layout of the pre-existing voice telephony network to minimize costs. Since the telecommunication data exploits historical peculiarities, the exogenous variation in the DSL roll-out can be used to exogenously estimate the effects of high-speed internet availability.

but cannot be explained by initial differences in firm size and workforce composition. This might suggest that the adoption of frontier technologies to a larger degree depends on having the right IT infrastructure as well as young (and technology-open) workers to implement the new technology.

For our analysis of changes in the occupation structure in Germany, these results point to significant initial differences in size and occupation structure between adopters and non-adopters and nuanced differences between digital adopters and frontier adopters. Initial period heterogeneity between adoption groups may also induce aggregate employment shifts across occupation groups, which we explore in our decomposition analysis.

Table B.3: Average marginal effects from a multinomial probit model

	Adopting digital technology (1)	Adopting frontier technology (2)
Manufacturing firm	-0.152** (0.062)	-0.103** (0.041)
Firm wage premium	0.003 (0.005)	-0.003 (0.002)
Firm employment	0.026 (0.019)	0.021*** (0.008)
MDF port within reach	-0.166 (0.102)	0.124** (0.052)
Worker shares by main task of occupation (reference: NRM)		
NRC	0.138 (0.089)	0.094** (0.047)
RC/RM	0.221*** (0.070)	0.065 (0.042)
Worker shares by required skill level (reference: Professionals)		
Experts	0.334*** (0.129)	0.023 (0.056)
Specialists	0.147 (0.105)	0.071 (0.052)
Unskilled workers	-0.294** (0.145)	0.071 (0.065)
Worker shares by age group (reference: 40-55 years of age)		
<40 years of age	-0.024 (0.091)	-0.077* (0.041)
>55 years of age	0.253 (0.156)	-0.153 (0.103)
Observations	1,660	1,660
Mean dep. variable	0.480	0.079

Notes: Columns show average marginal effects from a multinomial probit in column (1) for being a 3.0-adopter compared to being a non-adopter and column (2) for being a 4.0 adopter compared to a non-adopter. The variable set is equivalent to the one used in column (3) of Table B.2. Model estimated with firm stratification weights. NRC: non-routine cognitive jobs; RC/RM: Routine cognitive/manual jobs; NRM: non-routine manual jobs. Robust standard errors in parentheses. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

Appendix C Decomposition analysis: details

We extend the decomposition of Autor et al. (2020) and Acemoglu et al. (2020) by introducing sampling weights to account for the firm survey design, decomposing the residual changes in the covariance term and differentiating between more than two categories of firms.

Definitions

- λ_f – share of jobs in firm f with main task type $\lambda \in \{NRC, RM/RC, NRM\}$
- s_f – share of firm f in total employment, ignoring survey weights
- w_f – survey weight of firm f
- $F = \sum_{f \in F} w_f$ – number of firms (survey-weighted)
- $g \in (N, A^{digital}, A^{frontier})$ – groups of firms
- $G = \sum_{f \in g} w_f$ – number of firms in group g (survey-weighted). Note: $N + A^{digital} + A^{frontier} = F$
- $\tilde{s}_f = \frac{w_f s_f}{\sum_{f' \in F} w_{f'} s_{f'}}$ – employment share of firm f
- $\tilde{s}_g = \sum_{f \in g} \tilde{s}_f$ – share of group g in total employment
- $\bar{s} = \frac{1}{\sum_{f \in F} w_f} \sum_{f' \in F} \tilde{s}_{f'} = \frac{1}{F}$ – average employment share (= inverse number of firms)
- $\bar{s}_g = \frac{1}{\sum_{f \in g} w_f} \sum_{f' \in g} \tilde{s}_{f'} = \frac{\tilde{s}_g}{G}$ – average employment share of group g
- $\lambda = \sum_{f \in F} \frac{w_f s_f}{\sum_{f' \in F} w_{f'} s_{f'}} \lambda_f = \sum_{f \in F} \tilde{s}_f \lambda_f$ – aggregate employment share of jobs with main task type $\lambda \in \{NRC, RM/RC, NRM\}$
- $\bar{\lambda} = \frac{1}{F} \sum_{f \in F} w_f \lambda_f$ – firm-weighted average employment share of jobs with main task type $\lambda \in \{NRC, RM/RC, NRM\}$
- $\bar{\lambda}_g = \sum_{f \in g} w_f \lambda_f \frac{1}{F}$ – firm-weighted group-specific employment share of jobs with main task type $\lambda \in \{NRC, RM/RC, NRM\}$

We drop time indices for simplicity unless needed. Firm-weights w_f are time constant, and so are the numbers of firms.

Within firm variation and covariance

We decompose changes in aggregate employment shares of jobs with main task type $\lambda \in \{NRC, RM/RC, NRM\}$:

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta\lambda &= \lambda_t - \lambda_{t_0} = \sum_{f \in F} \tilde{s}_{ft} \lambda_{ft} - \sum_{f \in F} \tilde{s}_{ft_0} \lambda_{ft_0} \\
&= \sum_{f \in F} \left(\tilde{s}_{ft} \lambda_{ft} - \tilde{s}_{ft_0} \lambda_{ft_0} + \Delta\lambda_f \frac{w_f}{F} - \Delta\lambda_f \frac{w_f}{F} \right) \\
&= \Delta\bar{\lambda} + \sum_{f \in F} \left(\tilde{s}_{ft} \lambda_{ft} - \tilde{s}_{ft_0} \lambda_{ft_0} - \lambda_{ft} \frac{w_f}{F} + \lambda_{ft_0} \frac{w_f}{F} \right) \\
&= \Delta\bar{\lambda} + \Delta \sum_{f \in F} \left(\lambda_f \tilde{s}_f - \lambda_f \frac{w_f}{F} \right) \\
&= \Delta\bar{\lambda} + \Delta \sum_{f \in F} \lambda_f \left(\tilde{s}_f - \frac{w_f}{F} \right) \\
&= \Delta\bar{\lambda} + \Delta \sum_{f \in F} (\lambda_f - \bar{\lambda}) \left(\tilde{s}_f - \frac{w_f}{F} \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

for the last step, note that $\sum_{f \in F} \bar{\lambda} (\tilde{s}_f - \frac{w_f}{F}) = 0$.

We can split up the within component by groups:

$$\Delta\bar{\lambda} = \sum_g \Delta\bar{\lambda}_g \tag{11}$$

We can analogously split up the summation of the covariance part from $\sum_{f \in F}(\dots)$ into $\sum_g \sum_{f \in g}(\dots)$ to compute the covariance term separately for each group of firms.

Decomposing the covariance term

We decompose the covariance term of adopter group g :

$$\begin{aligned}
&\Delta \sum_{f \in g} (\lambda_f - \bar{\lambda}) \left(\tilde{s}_f - \frac{w_f}{F} \right) \\
&= \Delta \sum_{f \in g} \left[(\lambda_f - \bar{\lambda}) \left(\tilde{s}_f - \frac{w_f}{F} \right) - (\bar{\lambda}_g - \bar{\lambda}) \left(\tilde{s}_f - \frac{w_f}{F} \right) + (\bar{\lambda}_g - \bar{\lambda}) \left(\tilde{s}_f - \frac{w_f}{F} \right) \right] \\
&= \Delta \sum_{f \in g} \left[(\lambda_f - \bar{\lambda}_g) \left(\tilde{s}_f - \frac{w_f}{F} \right) + (\bar{\lambda}_g - \bar{\lambda}) \left(\tilde{s}_f - \frac{w_f}{F} \right) \right] \\
&= \Delta \sum_{f \in g} (\lambda_f - \bar{\lambda}_g) \left(\tilde{s}_f - \frac{w_f}{F} \right) + \Delta (\bar{\lambda}_g - \bar{\lambda}) \left(\tilde{s}_g - \frac{G}{F} \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

The first element is the within adoption groups effect, the second element is the between adoption groups effect.

Decomposing the within adoption groups effect

We further apply a shift-share decomposition to the within adoption groups effect:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \Delta \sum_{f \in g} \left(\lambda_f - \bar{\lambda}_g \right) \left(\tilde{s}_f - \frac{w_f}{F} \right) \\
&= \sum_{f \in g} \left(\tilde{s}_f - \frac{w_f}{F} \right) \Delta \left(\lambda_f - \bar{\lambda}_g \right) \\
&\quad + \sum_{f \in g} \left(\lambda_f - \bar{\lambda}_g \right) \Delta \left(\tilde{s}_f - \frac{w_f}{F} \right) \\
&\quad + \sum_{f \in g} \Delta \left(\lambda_f - \bar{\lambda}_g \right) \Delta \left(\tilde{s}_f - \frac{w_f}{F} \right)
\end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

For simplicity, we drop time indices – levels refer to initial levels, changes refer to changes between t and the initial time period. We denote the first element the (within adoption groups) scale effect, the second element the (within adoption groups) composition effect and the third element the (within adoption groups) simultaneous effect. We provide details on the interpretation of these three terms in the main paper.

Decomposing the between adoption groups effect

We analogously apply a shift-share decomposition to the between adoption groups effect:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \Delta \left(\bar{\lambda}_g - \bar{\lambda} \right) \left(\tilde{s}_g - \frac{G}{F} \right) \\
&= \left(\tilde{s}_g - \frac{G}{F} \right) \Delta \left(\bar{\lambda}_g - \bar{\lambda} \right) \\
&\quad + \left(\bar{\lambda}_g - \bar{\lambda} \right) \Delta \tilde{s}_g \\
&\quad + \Delta \left(\bar{\lambda}_g - \bar{\lambda} \right) \Delta \tilde{s}_g
\end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

Note that $\Delta \frac{G}{F} = 0$ by definition (constant firm weights). For simplicity, we drop time indices – levels refer to initial levels, changes refer to changes between t and the initial time period. We denote the first element the (between adoption groups) scale effect, the second element the (between adoption groups) composition effect, and the third element the (between adoption groups) simultaneous effect.

(1) We denote as '(between adoption groups) scale effect' employment shifts across the

three occupation groups λ that stem from differences in the initial average firm size between the three adoption groups in combination with differential average employment shifts across the three occupation groups λ among firms of the three adoption groups. As an example, if frontier adopters are larger than the average firm and at the same time decrease their routine job share, the initial size difference would amplify this effect and further decrease the overall routine employment share.

(2) We denote as '(between adoption groups) composition effect' employment shifts across the three occupation groups λ that result from differences in initial occupational-specific employment shares between the three adoption groups in combination with differential employment growth. For example, suppose frontier adopters have a higher routine employment share initially and at the same time experience lower employment growth than firms belonging to the other adoption groups. In that case, the '(between adoption groups) composition effect' would contribute to a declining overall routine employment share.

(3) We denote as '(between adoption groups) simultaneous effect' changes in firm size and changes in occupation-specific employment shares that take place simultaneously but differ on average between the adoption groups. If, as an example, frontier adopters grow faster and simultaneously reduce their routine employment share more pronounced than non-adopters and digital adopters, this reallocation between adoption groups is captured by the '(between adoption groups) simultaneous effect'.

Appendix D Decomposition analysis: additional results

Between group component for frontier adopters Figure D.1 shows that the between adoption groups component (second component in equation 4) plays a negligible role for frontier technology adopters' contribution to the changes in employment composition of the economy. This irrelevance aligns with three key observations:

(1) Adopters of frontier technologies are very similar in observable characteristics compared to the adopters of digital technologies (see Appendix Table A.3, columns 2-3, and Appendix Table B.2, columns 4-6).

(2) Although adopters of frontier technologies and non-adopters differ in their initial observable workforce characteristics (see Appendix Table A.3, columns 1 and 3), the employment growth rate between the average frontier adopter and non-adopter is very similar (see Appendix Figure D.2, panel b), making initial differences in the workforce composition irrelevant.

(3) The average frontier adopter does not reduce but rather (insignificantly) increases its routine employment share (see Figure 2) such that initial size differences between frontier and non-adopters (see Appendix Table A.3, columns 1 and 3 and Appendix Figure D.2, panel a) remain ineffective.

Figure D.1: Sources of the between adoption groups effect for frontier technology adopters

Notes: Decomposition of between-group component for frontier adopters as shown in equation (14): contribution of frontier adopters to aggregate de-routinization between 2011 and 2016 due to average differences between frontier adopters and other adoption groups related to size or composition. Scale, composition, and simultaneous components add up to the total between-group effect of frontier adopters. NRC: Non-routine cognitive tasks; RC/RM: Routine cognitive/manual tasks; NRM: Non-routine manual tasks. Confidence bands based on jackknife standard errors.

Figure D.2: Employment trends

Notes: Panel (a) displays the yearly employment levels between 2011 and 2016 by adoption groups. Panel (b) displays the normalized employment growth indexed at the 2011 employment levels. Employment figures are weighted with firm stratification weights.

Figure D.3: Contribution of digital adopters to aggregate de-routinization

Notes: Panel (a) reports the contribution to aggregate de-routinization between 2011 and 2016 by digital adopters differentiating between the three components from equation 4. Panel (b) reports a decomposition of within adoption groups component for digital adopters as shown in equation (13): contribution of digital adopters to aggregate de-routinization between 2011 and 2016 due to shifts induced between digital adopting firms related to size, composition differences, and a combination of both. Scale, composition, and simultaneous components add up to the total within adoption groups effect of digital adopters shown in Panel (a). NRC: non-routine cognitive jobs; RC/RM: routine cognitive/manual jobs; NRM: non-routine manual jobs. Confidence bands based on jackknife standard errors.

Figure D.4: Contribution of non-adopters to aggregate de-routinization

Notes: Panel (a) reports the contribution to aggregate de-routinization between 2011 and 2016 by non-adopters differentiating between the three components from equation 4. Panel (b) reports a decomposition of within adoption groups component for non-adopters as shown in equation (13): contribution of non-adopters to aggregate de-routinization between 2011 and 2016 due to shifts induced between non-adopting firms related to size, composition differences, and a combination of both. Scale, composition, and simultaneous components add up to the total within adoption groups effect of non-adopters shown in Panel (a). NRC: non-routine cognitive jobs; RC/RM: routine cognitive/manual jobs; NRM: non-routine manual jobs. Confidence bands based on jackknife standard errors.

Figure D.5: Contribution to overall de-routinization between 2011 and 2016

Notes: Panel (a) displays the contribution of each adoption group g to the aggregated occupational sifts between 2011 and 2016, which is the summation of components from equation 4 by adoption group g . The sum of the percentage changes across non-adopters, digital adopters and frontier adopters corresponds with the total percentage point changes for each task domain shown in Figure 1. Panel (b) displays the contribution of each component from equation 4 to the aggregated occupational sifts between 2011 and 2016. NRC: non-routine cognitive jobs; RC/RM: routine cognitive/manual jobs; NRM: non-routine manual jobs. Confidence bands based on jackknife standard errors.

Figure D.6: Skill shifts separately for each adoption group

Notes: Changes in the skill-specific employment shares between 2011 and 2016 separately for each adoption group g . High-skilled refers to individuals with a university degree, medium-skilled refers to workers with a vocational training qualification, and low-skilled refers to individuals without a vocational training degree. Confidence bands based on jackknife standard errors.

Figure D.7: Employment shifts across requirement level groups separately for each adoption group

Notes: Changes in the employment shares across requirement level groups between 2011 and 2016 separately for each adoption group g . The three groups refer to different job requirement categories as they are formally distinguished in the German occupation classification (KldB-2010, 5-digit). Experts and specialists refer to the most complex work activities on their jobs. Skilled workers conduct somewhat complex activities while unskilled workers conduct simple and non-complex activities. Confidence bands based on jackknife standard errors.

Figure D.8: Employment shifts across wage groups separately for each adoption group

Notes: Changes in the employment shares across wage groups between 2011 and 2016 separately for each adoption group g . High wage occupations are based in the 75th percentile or higher of the median wage distribution of all occupations in Germany in the year 2012. Medium wage occupations are ranked between the 25th and 75th percentile of the median wage distribution of all occupations in Germany in the year 2012. Low wage occupations are ranked below the 25th percentile of the median wage distribution of all occupations in Germany in the year 2012. Confidence bands based on jackknife standard errors.

Appendix E Decomposition analysis: robustness

We run a number of robustness checks on the decomposition of the employment de-routinization in Germany between 2011 and 2016. In particular, we repeat the decomposition analysis using alternative sample choices and definitions diverging from those of the main sample as explained in section 2.1. We test whether the key findings are robust to (a) using a different time span that is unaffected by a structural break of the occupational classification in 2011, (b) the exclusion of non-profit firms, (c) the exclusion of outliers in employment growth or decline, (d) an alternative classification of firms into adoption groups as used in Genz et al. (2021), (e) an alternative classification of firms into adoption groups using only contemporaneous information on the technology use in 2016 and (f) an alternative task measure based on the O*NET data. For each robustness check, we show the results corresponding to Figure 2 including the within-firm effect and Figure 3 for comparison with the main sample:

- (a) **Different time span.** We decompose the employment changes across the three occupational groups between 2012 and 2016 rather than between 2011 and 2016 as there was a change in the occupational classification between 2011 and 2012 that might result in a structural break. Resulting task changes are smaller because of the shorter time span, as expected, but the structural shifts are the same.

Figure E.1: De-routinization with new base year

- (b) **Excluding firms without revenues.** We exclude 110 firms that report to make no revenues. These establishments either belong to the public sector or are a non-profit

organization and might differ from the private, profit-oriented sector. When excluding these firms, we still find similar result patterns as for the main sample:

Figure E.2: De-routinization excluding firms without revenues

(c) **Excluding outliers in employment growth.** We exclude 24 establishments for which we observe outliers in employment growth across time. Such outliers may result from the in- or outsourcing of certain parts of the establishment which we cannot observe in the data. We thus exclude outliers, i.e., firms for which the annual employment growth in any of the years between 2011 and 2016 exceeds the 99th percentile plus one standard deviation (which corresponds to a growth factor of 4.4). We also exclude firms that lose more than 60% of their workforce (corresponding to the 1st percentile of the employment growth distribution) if the initial workforce size exceeds ten workers. Again, we find similar results.

Figure E.3: De-routinization excluding outliers in employment growth

(d) **Assigning adoption groups based on technology shares.** Rather than using the changes in net investments ΔI_{fg} to classify establishments, we classify in this robustness check establishments into non-adopters, digital and frontier adopters based on percentage changes in the technology-specific capital shares k_{fgt} as reported from the survey and shown in Appendix Table A.1. In this alternative classification, an establishment would be considered as frontier adopter if the share of frontier technologies increased more than the shares of other technology types. Table E.1 compares this alternative adoption group assignment (based on changes in technology shares Δk_{fgt}) with assignment used in the main analysis (based on changes in net investments ΔI_{fg}). See also Appendix Section B for a detailed comparison between both approaches.

Table E.1: Comparison between original and alternative adoption group assignments based on changes in technology shares

			Assignment based on technology shares (alternative)			
			non-adopters	digital adopters	frontier adopters	total
Assignment based on net investments (main analysis)	non-adopters	267	158	100	525	
	digital adopters	7	712	244	963	
	frontier adopters	0	7	165	172	
	total	274	877	509	1,660	

The comparison demonstrates that taking account of the capital stock and corresponding net investments results in a more restrictive assignment to the adopter groups. While there are only 172 frontier adopters in our main sample of analysis, using the capital shares as the basis for group assignment results in 509 adopters of frontier technologies. Our decomposition results nevertheless remain qualitatively robust.

Figure E.4: De-routinization when assigning adoption groups based on technology shares

One minor difference relates to the source of the between firm task shifts occurring within the group of frontier adopters. With the more generous assignment of a frontier adoption status, the heterogeneity between frontier adopters is mostly driven scale effects while the composition effect contributes less to the heterogeneity among firms belonging to the frontier adopter group.

- (e) **Assigning adoption groups based on 2016 technology use.** We now define our adoption groups based on the technology use in 2016 and refrain from using the retrospective information for the year 2011. For this, we define a firm to be a frontier adopter if the frontier technologies share in 2016 exceeds the 5th percentile of the corresponding distribution. Among the remaining firms, those whose digital technology share in 2016 exceeds the 5th percentile in the corresponding distribution are considered as digital adopters. All others are considered as non-adopters. We thus do not make any use of the retrospective information.

Table E.2: Comparison between original and alternative adoption group assignments based on technology use in 2016

			Assignment based on technology use in 2016 (alternative)			
			non-adopters	digital adopters	frontier adopters	total
Assignment based on net investments (main analysis)	non-adopters		417	91	17	525
	digital adopters		62	803	98	963
	frontier adopters		10	7	155	172
	total		489	901	270	1,660

Table E.2 shows that this alternative adoption group assignment is quite similar to the assignment based on net investments between 2011 and 2016. Moreover, decomposition results confirm the previous result pattern. Hence, results in our main analysis do not hinge on using the potentially unreliable, retrospective information.

Figure E.5: De-routinization when assigning adoption groups based on 2016 technology use

Notes: Panel (a) reports the contribution to aggregate employment shifts across task groups between 2011 and 2016 by frontier adopters differentiating between the three components from equation 4. Panel (b) reports a decomposition of within adoption groups component for frontier adopters as shown in equation (13): contribution of frontier adopters to aggregate employment shifts between 2011 and 2016 due to employment shifts induced between frontier adopting firms related to size, composition differences, and a combination of both. Scale, composition and simultaneous components add up to the total within adoption groups effect of frontier adopters shown in Panel (a). Confidence bands based on jackknife standard errors.

(f) **Main task assignment based on O*NET database.** Our classification of occupations is based on the main task at the 3-digit occupation level as reported from the German expert data base BERUFENET of the Federal Employment Agency (see section 2). As a robustness check, we classify firms according to the main task based on the task structure reported in the O*NET database. Since we have to conduct a crosswalk from the SOC occupation classification to the German KldB 2010, this alternative task measure introduces noise and accordingly leads to less strong task shifts, but the overall patterns remain.

Figure E.6: De-routinization with main task assignment based on O*NET database

Appendix F Delving into the heterogeneity among frontier adopters

Perceived chances and risks of frontier technologies

The survey contains a set of questions on how firms perceive the opportunities and risks of using frontier technologies. The exact wording of the question is: “If you think about the opportunities and risks linked to these technologies in an establishment like yours. What do you think is true?”. Firms were selected randomly to answer 8 out of the following 16 questions, see Appendix Table F.1. On average, each firm answered 7.85 questions and 91% answered all 8 questions they were randomly assigned to. As a result, we have between 782 to 830 non-missing answers for each question. Each question was answered using a 5-point scale from (1) this is absolutely true, (2) this is more likely to be the case (3) neither, (4) this rather does not apply, (5) this does not apply at all.

To use the firm’s perceptions as regressors in section 4, we impute the missing answers for each firm by exploiting the fact that each firm answered 8 out of 16 related questions that are likely to contain valuable correlated information. More precisely, we use a random forest classification for the binary information whether a firm fully agrees with the respective question or not.⁴⁵ We use the answers from all other perception measures as features. This is possible because we also include an additional missing dummy in case the respective perception measure is missing for firm f . Since the reason for missing perceptions is predominantly due to randomization, this is a feasible approach. In addition, the set of features includes firm and workforce characteristics and the firm’s capital structure as in Table 3. In total, we use 120 features. We run the random forest algorithm on the full sample of all firms for which we observe the dependent variable irrespective of the firm’s adoption status. Hence, the model also controls for adoption status to allow for a related heterogeneity in perceived chances and risks of adopting frontier technology. We further control for size to allow an additional size-related difference in perceptions.

Based on this model, we predict whether a firm fully agrees with each statement, and use this prediction for the regression analyses in section 4. Appendix Table F.1 includes several indicators for the observed perceptions and their imputed predictions including the out-of-bag (OOB) error as an indicator of the model’s predictive power. Overall, Appendix Table F.1 suggests a good fit of our imputation model.

⁴⁵Fine-tuning resulted in a random forest with 500 trees and several features per split which is equal to the square root of the total features, which resulted in the best out-of-sample error rate.

Table F.1: Questions on chances and risks related to frontier technologies

“The use of frontier technologies...”			predicted prob for score=1			
	obs	mean	share with	non-missing	missing	OBB error
this is absolutely true (score=1)		score	score = 1	N=obs	N=1660-obs	N=1,660
... this does not apply at all (score=5)	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
Chances						
<i>labprod</i> ... increases labor productivity	830	2.45	0.285	0.289	0.306	0.311
<i>indprod</i> ... enables customized products/services	814	2.61	0.273	0.284	0.308	0.305
<i>newprod</i> ... enables new products/services	813	2.77	0.223	0.235	0.279	0.257
<i>transcostr</i> ... reduces transport/warehousing costs	787	3.40	0.159	0.172	0.191	0.201
<i>labcostr</i> ... reduces labor costs	809	3.36	0.097	0.111	0.140	0.155
<i>bodystrainr</i> ... reduces workers’s physical strain	782	3.47	0.081	0.094	0.126	0.132
<i>energyocr</i> ... reduces energy costs	818	3.75	0.039	0.048	0.059	0.075
Risks						
<i>cybercosti</i> ... increases expenditures for cybersecurity	820	1.82	0.582	0.586	0.588	0.315
<i>trainneed</i> ... increases training needs	819	2.08	0.421	0.424	0.433	0.365
<i>invcost</i> ... comes with high investment costs	834	2.16	0.364	0.362	0.349	0.356
<i>traincont</i> ... changes the training content	830	2.46	0.347	0.355	0.374	0.342
<i>extdep</i> ... increases dependence on external firms	838	2.56	0.325	0.318	0.311	0.263
<i>mentstraini</i> ... increases worker’s mental strain	784	2.98	0.225	0.215	0.189	0.156
<i>restruc</i> ... necessitates complex reorganization of firm	802	3.05	0.175	0.193	0.232	0.234
<i>labshort</i> ... is hampered by a shortage of skilled labor	849	3.15	0.171	0.184	0.197	0.187
<i>econriski</i> ... increases economic risks of firm	802	3.35	0.143	0.140	0.129	0.089

Notes: Perceptions are observed for the number of firms in column (1). Column (2) gives the observed average value of the 5-point scale for each perception, while column (3) reports the share of firms that fully agree (score=1). Columns (4)-(5) report the results from the predictions based on the random forest classification, i.e., the probability to fully agree (score=1) for the sub-sample of firms for which we also observe the perception (column 4) and the sub-sample of firms for which perceptions are missing (column 5). Column (6) displays the Out-Of-Bag error. All statistics are weighted with firm-stratification weights.

Skill demands

The survey contains a set of questions asking firms to assess whether they consider certain skill requirements to have decreased, remained stable, or increased. The exact wording of the question is: “If you think about the requirements that a job in your company entails. Please estimate which of the following requirements have gained or lost importance in the last five years.” For time reasons, firms were randomly selected to answer this question for half of the 14 skill types listed in Appendix Table F.2. On average, each firm answered 6.98 and 98.5% answered the question for all 7 items they were randomly assigned to. For each item, firms could assess based on a 5-point scale whether the respective skill (1) strongly declined, (2) somewhat declined, (3) neither declined nor increased, (4) somewhat increased, and (5) strongly increased in importance during the last five years. Additionally, a firm could also answer that the skill is irrelevant in their firm.

To use these assessments as regressors in section 4, we impute the missing items for each firm by exploiting the fact that each firm answered about half of the 14 items which are likely to contain valuable correlated information. More precisely, we use a random forest to classify whether a firm considers the importance of the respective skill to have strongly increased or not.⁴⁶ For this, we use all other skill requirements as features of the model. This is possible because we also include an additional dummy in case the respective item is missing for firm f . Since the reason for missing items is predominantly due to randomization, this is a feasible approach. Moreover, we add estimated probabilities that certain skills are irrelevant.⁴⁷ In addition, the set of features includes firm and workforce characteristics as well as the firm’s capital structure as in Table 3. We also add interactions between the adoption status and the initial employment shares across occupational groups. In total, we use 126 features in the random forest classification.

Based on this model, we predict the probability that a firm considers a certain skill requirement to have increased strongly in importance during the last five years. We use these predictions in section 4. The indicators for the observed and predicted skill requirements in Appendix Table F.2, as well as the Out-Of-Bag error rate suggest a good fit of our imputation model.

⁴⁶Fine-tuning resulted in a random forest with 300 trees and several features per split which is equal to the square root of the total features, which resulted in the best out-of-sample error rate.

⁴⁷For this, we first run a random forest classifier to estimate the probability that a certain skill is considered irrelevant by the firm. For this classification, we use the information on the irrelevance of the other observable skills (plus dummies if the answer is missing due to randomization of items). We do so only for a subset of skills for which at least 4% of all firms report the skill to be irrelevant in their firm. This only applies to *phystress*, *mandext*, *creativity*, *envknow*, *developIT*, and *interdisc*.

Table F.2: Questions on changes in skill demands

“The importance of [<i>skill</i>] during the last five years has ...”					predicted prob for score=5		
strongly declined (score=1)	obs	mean	share with	non-missing	missing	OBB error	
...		score	score = 5	N=obs	N=1660-obs	N=1,660	
strongly increased (score=5)	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	
<i>knowIT</i>	knowledge in the application of IT	815	4.21	0.371	0.325	0.279	0.271
<i>developIT</i>	development of IT	822	4.07	0.255	0.173	0.144	0.233
<i>learning</i>	learning new skills and competencies	842	4.03	0.225	0.215	0.212	0.212
<i>multitask</i>	multitasking	842	3.83	0.209	0.198	0.209	0.199
<i>dealcustom</i>	dealing with customers	828	3.73	0.193	0.200	0.210	0.184
<i>mentstress</i>	working under high mental stress	829	3.74	0.183	0.174	0.189	0.167
<i>envknow</i>	environmental protection knowledge	830	3.85	0.182	0.148	0.122	0.163
<i>indwork</i>	independent working	800	3.71	0.151	0.171	0.179	0.186
<i>creative</i>	creativity	832	3.60	0.126	0.118	0.113	0.102
<i>physstress</i>	working under high physical stress	843	3.31	0.124	0.096	0.089	0.062
<i>knowproc</i>	process know-how	849	3.72	0.122	0.128	0.155	0.188
<i>interdisc</i>	interdisciplinary working	801	3.65	0.121	0.110	0.115	0.144
<i>leadersh</i>	leadership skills	836	3.62	0.120	0.127	0.133	0.148
<i>mandext</i>	manual dexterity	814	3.08	0.025	0.022	0.032	0.023

Notes: The change in importance of the skill requirements is observed for the number of firms in column (1). Column (2) gives the observed average value of the 5-point scale as described above, while column (3) reports the share of firms that suggest the respective skill requirement to have gained strongly in importance (score=5). Columns (4)-(5) report the results from the predictions based on the ordered logit model, i.e. the probability to consider the skill requirement to have gained strongly in importance (score=5) for the sub-sample of firms for which we also observe the perception (column 4) and the sub-sample of firms for which perceptions are missing (column 5). Column (6) displays the Out-Of-Bag error. All statistics are weighted with firm-stratification weights.

Training needs

The survey contains a set of questions asking firms to assess how vocational and further training changed in the five past years with respect to a number of different dimensions. In particular, firms are asked whether they agree to 10 different dimensions on a 5-point scale from (1) this is absolutely true, (2) this is more likely to be the case (3) neither, (4) this rather does not apply, (5) this does not apply at all. Appendix Table F.3 includes the statements firm's were asked to assess. However, firms were only asked to answer the questions if they offered vocational training and further training within the last five years. Accordingly, in contrast to firms' perceptions and skill requirements, items are not missing at random. However, using imputed training items vs. training items and a dummy indicator when those items are missing shows that our results in the main paper remain robust.

In order to use these assessments as regressors in section 4, we impute the missing items for each firm by using the information on all other training measures (including a dummy in case the respective item is missing for firm f). In addition, the set of features includes firm and workforce characteristics as well as the firm's capital structure as in Table 3. We run the random forest algorithm on the full sample of all firms for which we observe the dependent variable irrespective of the firm's adoption status.⁴⁸ Hence, the model also controls for adoption status to allow for a related heterogeneity in perceived development in vocational and further training. We further control for size to allow an additional size-related difference in perceptions. In total, we use 85 features in the random forest classification.

Based on this model, we predict the probability that a firm fully agrees with the respective statement about trends in training. We use these predictions in section 4. The indicators for the observed and predicted training indicators in Appendix Table F.3 suggests a good fit of our imputation model.

⁴⁸Fine-tuning resulted in a random forest with 500 trees and several features per split which is equal to the square root of the total features, which resulted in the best out-of-sample error rate.

Table F.3: Questions on changes in vocational and further training needs

“Which of the following statements do you agree/disagree with?”				predicted prob for score=1					
				obs	mean score	share with score = 1	non-missing N=obs	missing N=1660-obs	OBB error N=1,660
this is absolutely true (score=1)				(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
...									
this does not apply at all (score=5)									
<i>If you think of the vocational training in your firm.</i>									
<i>voctinterc</i>	We increasingly train intercurricular skills.	1016	2.16	0.34	0.320	0.255	0.227		
<i>voctICT</i>	We increasingly train ICT-skills.	1026	2.44	0.32	0.319	0.317	0.205		
<i>voctcont</i>	The training content has changed in the last 5 years.	1003	2.54	0.25	0.235	0.164	0.179		
<i>voctmism</i>	The mismatch between required and actual skills increases.	1010	3.34	0.14	0.136	0.124	0.059		
<i>voctnew</i>	We train in other fields/occupations than in the past.	1027	4.03	0.04	0.051	0.057	0.077		
<i>If you think about further training in your firm.</i>									
<i>traincost</i>	The costs for further training have increased.	1291	2.30	0.29	0.297	0.292	0.285		
<i>trainICT</i>	We increasingly train ICT skills .	1295	2.65	0.26	0.253	0.220	0.205		
<i>trainhqual</i>	Our workers can more easily get higher qualifications.	1296	3.08	0.15	0.146	0.116	0.160		
<i>trainelearn</i>	We increasingly use E-Learning tools.	1303	3.38	0.12	0.137	0.121	0.170		
<i>traininterc</i>	We increasingly train intercurricular skills.	1303	3.00	0.11	0.118	0.113	0.142		

Notes: The assessment of the respective statement is observed for the number of firms in column (1). Column (2) gives the observed average value of the 5-point scale as described above, while column (3) reports the share of firms that fully agree with this statement (score=1). Columns (4)-(5) report the results from the predictions based on the random forest classification, i.e. the probability to fully agree to the respective statement (score=1) for the sub-sample of firms for which we also observe the answer (column 4) and the sub-sample of firms for which the answer is missing (column 5). Column (6) displays the Out-Of-Bag error. All statistics are weighted with firm-stratification weights.

Competition, Markups, and Automation*

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Abstract

In this paper we provide new long-run evidence on market concentration, markups, and automation by focusing on the case of Spain. We present three main insights derived from firm-level data. First, markets targeted by Spanish firms have become significantly more competitive over the period 1990-2018, and the top firms in the manufacturing sector have seen their market shares stagnate over time. Second, output prices and marginal costs of firms have evolved in tandem since 1991, such that the average markup in the manufacturing industry has been rather flat. In contrast to the evidence found for other countries, especially the U.S., markups among the top firms have not been rising over the period 1991-2018. Finally, automation comes with higher average markups, an effect that, as we show, is fully explained by the productivity gains associated with automation. Specifically, we find that automation reduces the firm's marginal cost, which translates into a lower output price, but the price reduction is less than proportional, so that the firm's markup rises.

JEL codes: D24, L11, O33

Keywords: markups, market power, competition, automation, technology, productivity

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1 Introduction

Several influential papers have uncovered declining labor shares and rising markups in the US and other advanced economies over the last few decades (De Loecker et al., 2020; De Loecker and Eeckhout, 2021). These observations have been linked to the phenomenon of “superstar firms” triggered by globalization and technology (Autor et al., 2020). As shown by Acemoglu and Restrepo (2018, 2022) and Acemoglu et al. (2020), automation technologies have the potential to widen inequality between both workers and firms. Recently, new evidence on the link between automation technologies and rising concentration and markups has started to emerge (Hubmer and Restrepo, 2024; Firooz et al., 2023).

In this paper we provide new long-run evidence on market concentration, markups, and automation by focusing on the case of Spain. The central insights from our paper are as follows. First, markets targeted by Spanish firms have become significantly more competitive over the period 1990-2018, and the top firms in the manufacturing sector have not been able to capture larger market shares over time. Second, output prices and marginal costs of firms have evolved in tandem since 1991, such that the average markup (price over marginal cost) in the manufacturing industry has been rather flat. Importantly, we do not find evidence for rising markups among the top firms over the period 1991-2018. Finally, automation comes with higher markups at the firm level, an effect explained fully by the productivity gains associated with automation. Specifically, we find empirically that automation reduces the firm’s marginal cost, which translates into a lower output price, but the price reduction is less than proportional, so that the firm’s markup rises.

To arrive at these results, we conduct a variety of analyses bringing together data from different sources. In particular, our paper is structured in three parts. In the first part, we consult firm-level survey data along with industry-level administrative data in order to provide a broad macro view on the evolution of market shares and market concentration since the 1990s. The picture we provide is different from other types of analyses as the firms in our survey data set (ESEE) are free to define markets on their own terms (by products, customer groups, or other characteristics firms find relevant). To complete the picture we obtain based on the ESEE survey data, we draw in official industry-level data on the evolution of the number of firms, the firm size distribution, and revenues from the Spanish National Statistics Office (INE).

In the second part of the paper, we compute, and explore, changes in firm-level markups over the period 1991-2018. A novelty of our analysis relative to the existing literature is that the ESEE data set allows us to decompose changes in markups into changes in output prices and changes in marginal costs. This is made possible by the fact that output price changes are observed directly in the data, and by exploiting the first-order condition of a variable input in the firm’s cost minimization problem (Hall, 1988). Disentangling price and cost changes seems important in order to understand and pin down the sources of markup changes over time. A focus of this part of the analysis is also on how markups have evolved, not just on average, but also at the top of the markup distribution, to investigate potential “superstar effects”.

In the final part of the paper, we zoom in explicitly on the micro-level of our data to investigate

the relationship between markups and automation over time. Apart from being able to compute firm-level changes in markups, prices, and marginal costs based on the ESEE survey data, we also observe a direct measure of automation over nearly three decades (viz. whether the firm uses robots in its production process). To the best of our knowledge, our paper is the first to analyse empirically the relationship between automation on the one hand and markups, prices, and marginal costs on the other hand over a long time period capturing the adoption and diffusion of automation technology in the manufacturing industry.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Section 2 we introduce the data that we use and provide descriptive analyses. In Section 3 we explain how we compute markups and we document some patterns in the data. In Section 4 we present our micro-level analysis on automation and markups, prices, and marginal costs. Section 5 concludes.

2 Data and Descriptive Analyses

Our data derive from the Encuesta Sobre Estrategias Empresariales (ESEE). This is an annual survey of roughly 1,900 firms active in the manufacturing sector in Spain.¹ We analyze the data for the period 1990-2018 and are thus able to paint a detailed picture of the evolution of the manufacturing sector and firm activities over almost three decades. The sampling of the data in 1990 had a two-tier structure taking into account the size of firms measured by the number of employees.² Specifically, survey questionnaires were sent out to all large firms that had more than 200 employees, and to a sample of small firms that had between 10 and 200 employees. Small firms were chosen based on stratified, proportional and systematic sampling with a random seed, where a firm’s industry affiliation and size class were used as stratification variables. The survey distinguishes between 20 different industries, where each industry is given by a set of 3-digit NACE Rev. 2 products. The sampling of the data is done in such a way that the ESEE data are representative of the Spanish manufacturing sector at large when the sampling properties are taken into account. To do so, we use sampling weights that reflect the inverse sampling probability of a firm relative to the population of firms by industry-size stratum in 2010, based on data from the Spanish Instituto Nacional de Estadística (INE).

Is there evidence for superstar firms in the ESEE survey data?—In the first part of the analysis, we portray the evolution of market shares and market concentration between 1990 and 2018. To do so, we exploit survey questions on *(i)* firms’ market shares in different markets; and *(ii)* the number of competitors and their market shares in these markets. The purpose of this part of the analysis is to see whether there has been a tendency in the data for rising market shares at the top of the sales distribution and an overall decline in the degree of competition with fewer companies and stronger market positions of a few dominant firms (“superstar firms”).

¹The ESEE is conducted by the SEPI foundation (Sociedad Estatal de Participaciones Industriales). See <https://www.fundacionsepi.es/investigacion/esee/en/spresentacion.asp> for details on the survey and how to access the data.

²Over time, refreshment samples are incorporated so that new firms are added to the survey as other firms exit.

Specifically, firms in the survey report their own market shares as well as the market shares of their competitors in their most important markets (up to five markets that together make up at least 50% of the firm’s total sales). As an important difference to the use of administrative data, in the ESEE data firms are free to define a market on their own terms, that is, they can define a market along the lines of products, types of customers, or other characteristics they deem relevant.

Figure 1a shows that, overall, the average market share of firms in the single most important market they serve has been on a declining trend over the period 1990-2016. Only in the last two years of our sample period, between 2016 and 2018, do we see an increase in the average market share reported by firms. In the beginning of the 1990s the average market share stood at around 10%, and came down to 3.8% in 2016. We observe a similar trend for the top decile of market shares, with a declining trend between 1990 and 2016, and a rebound between 2016 and 2018. To dig deeper into the possibility that the most dominant firms have been able to crowd out their competitors, Figure 1b shows the evolution of market shares depending on the reporting firm’s own position in the market (1st, 2nd, or 3rd market leader). That is, the figure focuses exclusively on the top-performing firms in the single most important market reported by the firm. We observe rather stable market shares for these firms over the entire period of analysis, and no indication of rising market shares at the top of the sales distribution. We get a similar impression when looking at the data for the other markets reported by the firms in our sample, that is, the 2nd, 3rd, 4th, and 5th most important markets. Figure A.1 in the Appendix shows average market shares and market shares for the top decile of the distribution; Figure A.2 shows average market shares for just the market leaders in their respective markets. If anything, the data show that market shares at the top have been declining, rather than rising, over time.

Figure 2 exploits data on the number of competitors in the single most important market reported by firms. Firms report whether there are 10 or less competitors, 11-25 competitors, more than 25 competitors, or whether the market is “atomized” (i.e. competitive).³ The figure shows that the share of firms reporting a competitive market has been rising from less than 20% in 1991 to more than 50% in 2017 (and even 80% in 2018). The rise has been particularly steep since 2010. All other categories, including the one with 10 or less competitors, have been declining over time. We see strikingly similar pictures when looking at the firms’ 2nd, 3rd, 4th, and 5th most important markets; see Figure A.3 in the Appendix. Overall, we thus observe a clear shift towards more competitive markets in Spanish manufacturing since 1990, and no evidence for superstar firms becoming more dominant players in their markets over time.

³This last option was added to the survey in 1991 and was not available in 1990, which is why the figure omits the relevant data points in 1990.

Figure 1: Evolution of market shares (1990-2018).[†]

[†]Note: This figure shows the evolution of market shares as reported by firms in the ESEE data. Panel (a) shows average market shares as well as market shares for the top decile of firms. Panel (b) shows market shares of the top three firms in their respective markets. Sampling weights apply. *Source:* Authors' illustration using ESEE data.

Figure 2: Evolution of market concentration (1990-2018).[†]

[†]Note: This figure shows the evolution of market concentration for the most important market as reported by firms in the ESEE data. Sampling weights apply. *Source:* Authors' illustration using ESEE data.

Is there evidence for superstar firms in administrative data?—The data we use above are survey data from a sample of manufacturing firms. To see whether the absence of evidence for superstar effects is confirmed in administrative data, we resort to industry-level information available from the Spanish Instituto Nacional de Estadística (INE).

We start by inspecting data on the number of manufacturing firms by industry. These data

from the Structural Business Statistics are available for the period 1993-2022.⁴ Due to a change in industry classification from NACE rev. 1 to NACE rev. 2, we show the data separately for two periods, viz. 1993-2007 and 2008-2022.⁵ In Figure 3a we compute the inverse number of firms by industry and year, and then take the (revenue-weighted) average across industries for each year. The data show a decline in this measure over time. If markets were equally apportioned across firms, this would imply a decline in the average market share over time.

Figure 3: Average inverse number of firms and firm size distribution.[†]

[†]Note: Panel (a) shows the inverse number of firms averaged across 94 NACE rev. 1 industries (1993-2007) and across 119 NACE rev. 2 industries (2008-2022), respectively. Panel (b) shows the number of firms by size group (measured by the number of employees) across all manufacturing industries in 1999, 2010, and 2020, respectively. Source: Authors' illustration using INE data.

We next look into the evolution of the firm size distribution in Spanish manufacturing over time. For this purpose, we use data available since 1999 and compare the firm size distribution in the initial year with the ones in 2010 and 2020, respectively.⁶ Firm size groups are defined by the number of employees.⁷ Figure 3b shows that in each year the firm size distribution is strongly right-skewed with many small firms and few large firms. Over time, the number of firms has been declining in all size groups except for the biggest firms (those with more than 199 employees) whose number increased between 2010 and 2020 (but was still smaller in 2020 than in 1999).

Unfortunately, we do not have revenue data available by size group for the entire period. This makes it impossible to paint a comprehensive picture of how market shares at the top of the firm size distribution have evolved. However, we have the necessary revenue data available for the period

⁴They can be accessed at https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736143952&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735576715.

⁵For the first (second) period, we retain 94 (119) industries for which complete data are available across all years.

⁶These data from the Central Business Register (CBR) can be accessed at https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/en/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736160707&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735576550.

⁷We discard firms with less than 10 employees and only keep industries that we can consistently map across the three years.

2015-2022. Since firm-level market shares cannot be computed exactly, we proceed as follows: We compute the revenue share of each size group by industry, and then apportion this share equally across firms falling into the respective size group. We finally compute a (revenue-weighted) average across industries for each size group. Figure 4 shows the evolution of the thus defined market shares for the big firms (50-249 employees) and the biggest firms (more than 249 employees). We find a clear negative trend in market shares for these firms, and no evidence for superstar effects.

Figure 4: Average market share by size group (2015-2022).[†]

[†]Note: This figure shows the evolution of average market shares by firm size group for the period 2015-2022. *Source:* Authors' illustration using INE data.

3 Computing Markups

3.1 Framework

Our central object of interest is the firm-level markup (as a measure of market power) defined as $\mu_{it} \equiv P_{it}/\lambda_{it}$, where P_{it} is the output price of firm i at time t and λ_{it} is the firm's marginal cost. A markup greater than one means that the firm charges a price that exceeds its marginal cost and the firm has some market power. Specifically, we are interested in the *change* in the markup over time:

$$\hat{\mu}_{it} = \hat{P}_{it} - \hat{\lambda}_{it}, \tag{1}$$

where a 'hat' indicates percentage changes. Our data includes explicit information on annual output price changes at the firm level (i.e., \hat{P}_{it}), while changes in marginal cost ($\hat{\lambda}_{it}$) are unobserved. To get an expression for $\hat{\lambda}_{it}$ that can be obtained from our data, we derive the *level* of the firm's marginal cost (i.e., λ_{it}) as the shadow value in the firm's cost minimization problem (Hall, 1988). Specifically, we assume that production of firm i at time t takes place according to the following production

function:

$$Q_{it} = Q(L_{it}, M_{it}, K_{it}; \Omega_{it}), \quad (2)$$

where Q_{it} is units of output, L_{it} , M_{it} , and K_{it} are units of labor, intermediates, and capital, respectively, and Ω_{it} is a vector describing the firm's underlying production technology. This technology vector includes both Hicks-neutral and factor-biased productivity terms, as well as other parameters linked to the use of automation technology, in particular the range of automatable tasks and the complexity of the production process (Acemoglu and Restrepo, 2018). Importantly, *all* technology parameters in Ω_{it} are allowed to be *it*-specific so that each firm is allowed to have its own technology trajectory in all relevant dimensions.

We denote exogenous input prices corresponding to labor, intermediates, and capital by p^L , p^M , and p^K , respectively. We assume that intermediates M_{it} are *flexible*, that is, they can be adjusted instantaneously at zero cost.⁸ In contrast, the labor input L_{it} and the capital input K_{it} are both treated as *fixed* inputs. Hence, the optimal input demand choice of the firm at time t that we derive below is going to be *conditional* on both the labor input and the available capital stock at time t , and it will be sufficient to study the firm's cost minimization problem in terms of a static optimization problem. Specifically, to produce a certain level of output \bar{Q}_{it} , the firm minimizes its production cost C_{it} by solving

$$\min_{M_{it}} \{C_{it} = p_{it}^L L_{it} + p_{it}^M M_{it} + p_{it}^K K_{it}\} \quad (3)$$

subject to $Q(L_{it}, M_{it}, K_{it}; \Omega_{it}) \geq \bar{Q}_{it}$.⁹ This cost-minimization problem can be re-written as:

$$\min_{M_{it}, \lambda_{it}} \{ \mathcal{L}_{it} = p_{it}^L L_{it} + p_{it}^M M_{it} + p_{it}^K K_{it} + \lambda_{it} [\bar{Q}_{it} - Q(\cdot)] \} \quad (4)$$

where \mathcal{L}_{it} is the Lagrangian function and λ_{it} is the Lagrange multiplier, respectively. We can then write down the first-order condition for intermediates as follows:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_{it}}{\partial M_{it}} = p_{it}^M - \lambda_{it} \frac{\partial Q(\cdot)}{\partial M_{it}} \stackrel{!}{=} 0 \Rightarrow \frac{\partial Q(\cdot)}{\partial M_{it}} \frac{M_{it}}{Q_{it}} = \frac{p_{it}^M M_{it}}{\lambda_{it} Q_{it}}, \quad (5)$$

where λ_{it} is the shadow price in the cost minimization problem, that is, the marginal cost of production $\frac{\partial C_{it}}{\partial Q(\cdot)}$. Note that the left-hand side of the last equation is the output elasticity with respect to intermediates. We denote this variable by θ_{it}^M . Optimal firm behavior thus dictates that θ_{it}^M be equal to the respective input share when evaluating output at marginal cost. Let ϕ_{it}^M denote the total expenses on intermediates. By re-arranging terms, we can then re-write (5) as:

$$\hat{\lambda}_{it} = \hat{\phi}_{it}^M - \hat{Q}_{it} - \hat{\theta}_{it}^M, \quad (6)$$

⁸Alternatively, we can treat both labor and capital as fixed inputs in the production process.

⁹The virtue of this approach is that it relies only on cost-minimizing behavior of firms, but does not impose any assumptions on the type of competition the firm faces.

where a ‘hat’ indicates percentage changes. Equation (6) relates changes in the firm’s marginal cost to changes in (i) the firm’s factor bill ($\hat{\phi}_{it}^M$), (ii) the firm’s output (\hat{Q}_{it}), and (iii) the firm’s output elasticity ($\hat{\theta}_{it}^M$). From our data, we can compute (i) and (ii) directly, while (iii) is often estimated using a production function approach. For a Cobb-Douglas production function, as is often assumed in the literature (Peters, 2020; Crouzet and Eberly, 2021; Meier and Reinelt, 2024), the output elasticity is constant so that (iii) is zero and (6) simplifies to $\hat{\lambda}_{it} = \hat{\phi}_{it}^\ell - \hat{Q}_{it}$. Note that even under the Cobb-Douglas assumption the literature can usually not identify $\hat{\lambda}_{it}$, as firm-level changes in *real* output (i.e., \hat{Q}_{it}) are rarely observed in the data.¹⁰ In contrast, since we observe \hat{P}_{it} along with the value of output $V_{it} \equiv P_{it}Q_{it}$, we can compute $\hat{Q}_{it} = \hat{V}_{it} - \hat{P}_{it}$ for use in (6).¹¹

In the following, we exploit the rich information in our data to compute the output elasticity directly without having to estimate production functions. Specifically, we compute θ_{it}^M (and thus $\hat{\theta}_{it}^M$) directly from the data as the firm’s material cost share. This requires assuming constant returns to scale, but prevents us from having to estimate production functions, which would come with additional assumptions. Importantly, we can depart from the assumption, customarily made in the literature, that firms in the same industry share the same underlying technology vector (leaving aside between-firm differences in Hicks-neutral productivity). Instead we allow firms to have heterogeneous technology paths in all dimensions, by tracking their changes in cost shares (and thus output elasticities) over time. Moreover, we can track separately the evolution of prices, marginal costs, and markups, which implies that we can attribute changes in the markup to changes in the firm’s output price on the one hand, and changes in its marginal cost on the other hand. We can also compute the level of the markup, but not the level of the price and the marginal cost, respectively.

3.2 Evolution of Prices, Marginal Costs, and Markups

We now turn to a brief exploration of the thus obtained time series on prices, marginal costs, and markups. In Figure 5 we normalize all series to equal one in 1991, and then link the average annual percentage changes through to 2018. We see a pretty strong comovement of rising prices and marginal costs over time, implying a rather flat markup evolution. Price and cost increases were steep in the years leading up to the financial crisis, and more moderate since then. Prices and marginal costs were both about 50% higher (in nominal terms) in 2018 than in 1991, implying that the markup was of the same magnitude at the end of our sample period as it was in the beginning. Overall, there is no evidence for a rise in average markups over the three decades that we cover with our sample.

Our data also allow us to compute markup *levels*, even though a firm’s price level and its level of marginal cost is unobserved. In Figure 6 we show the evolution of markup levels over the period

¹⁰The literature typically uses an industry-level price index to deflate output. This negates firm-level heterogeneity in the evolution of output prices.

¹¹Note that V_{it} refers to the value of *production*, as observed in the data, not to the *revenue* of the firm. Note also that, as usual, neither the output price level P_{it} nor the physical units of output Q_{it} are observed in the data.

Figure 5: Evolution of prices, marginal costs, and markups (1991-2018)

Note: The figure shows the evolution of nominal prices, nominal marginal costs, and markups from 1991 to 2018 computed from the ESEE data as described in the text. The price and marginal cost series are computed by linking the average annual percentage changes through time. The price and marginal cost data are winsorized at the top and bottom 1 percent of observations in each year before computing the markup. All three series are sales-weighted and normalized to one in 1991. Sampling weights apply. *Source:* Authors' illustration using ESEE data.

1991-2018. To focus first on the average and the typical markup in the manufacturing sector in Spain, panel (a) displays the (sales-weighted) average and median markup levels. We see that both series fluctuate somewhat between 1.0 and 1.1. Overall, it is difficult to discern a clear trend in the data for either average or median markups. Interestingly, the average markup has been increasing since 2012, reaching an all-time high close to 1.12 in the last year of the sample period. However, it had previously been going down for several consecutive years in the wake of the 2008 financial crisis. In panel (b), we depict the evolution of markups at the top of the markup distribution, i.e., the markup levels for the 80th, 90th, and 95th percentiles. As before, there is no clear trend visible in the data. This demonstrates that, over the long period we consider here, markups have not been subject to a rising trend at the very top of the distribution.

Figure 6: Evolution of markup levels (1991-2018).[†]

[†]Note: This figure shows the evolution of markup levels from 1991 to 2018 computed from the ESEE data as described in the text. The data are trimmed at the top and bottom 1 percent of observations in each year and sales-weighted. Sampling weights apply. *Source:* Authors' illustration using ESEE data.

4 Markups and Automation

We now turn to our micro-level empirical application, whether automated firms have higher markups and whether markups change when firms start automating. This application is made possible by the fact that the ESEE data set includes a direct question on whether firms use robots in their production process or not. For further details on the survey question and some descriptive explorations of the variable, see Koch et al. (2021). In the following, we first discuss cross-sectional results, and then turn to the time series dimension of our data where we explore whether markups change when firms start using robots in their production process.

Do automated firms have different markups?—Since we have firm-specific markups, we can use a simple regression framework to investigate the relationship between a firm's markup and its automation status, that is, whether or not it is using robots in its production process. Our focus is the markup *difference* (in percent) between automated and non-automated firms. We run the following regression to explore this issue:

$$\ln \mu_{it} = \alpha + \beta \text{Automated}_{it} + \mathbf{X}_{it}^T \boldsymbol{\gamma} + \varepsilon_{it}, \quad (7)$$

where Automated_{it} is a 0/1 indicator for the use of robots¹², α is a constant, \mathbf{X}_{it}^T is a row vector of control variables, $\boldsymbol{\gamma}$ is the corresponding column vector of parameters to be estimated, and ε_{it} is the error term. The central parameter of interest is β , which captures the relationship between automation and markups and, more precisely, gives the percentage markup premium for automated

¹²The raw data reports the variable every four years since 1990. To keep all firm-year observations in the analysis, we interpolate the variable by carrying forward the last value of the variable for three years.

firms. As controls, we include the firm’s input variables in logs (labor, capital, and materials) to account for size differences between firms as well as differences in factor intensities. In addition, we include different sets of fixed effects to take out variation across industries, regions, and years, as well as combinations thereof. This means that we control for markup shocks even if they are specific to industries and regions in Spain. We emphasize that we do not lend a causal interpretation to β , but rather test whether automated firms have, on average, different markups than non-automated firms.

Table 1 reports the results based on varying sets of fixed effects. We find positive and highly significant estimates of β demonstrating significant markup differences between automated and non-automated firms. The estimates imply a markup premium for automated firms in the vicinity of one percent. The differences across the various fixed effect specifications are rather small and indicate that the markup premium cannot be explained by industry- or region-specific trends. We should like to stress that differences in firm size and factor intensities cannot explain the markup premium either, as they are controlled for throughout. The markup premium of one *percent* translates almost one by one into an *absolute* markup difference of 0.01, as we find an average markup around $\mu = 1$ for non-automated firms (captured by the constant α included in (7)).

Table 1: Pooled sample (OLS)

	Dependent variable: Markup (in logs)			
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Automated	0.0120*** (0.00296)	0.0119*** (0.00290)	0.0116*** (0.00292)	0.00975*** (0.00307)
Industry-year FE	No	Yes	Yes	Nested
Region-year FE	No	No	Yes	Nested
Industry-region-year FE	No	No	No	Yes
Observations	41460	41460	41458	39859
R-squared	0.029	0.098	0.112	0.221

Note: The dependent variable in all regressions is the firm-level markup (in logs). All regressions include the firm’s inputs in logs (labor, capital, and materials) as control variables. Robust standard errors are clustered at the level of the individual firm and are given in parentheses. *, **, *** denote significance at the 10%, 5%, 1% levels, respectively.

A candidate explanation for the level difference in markups found above are productivity differences between firms. Automated firms are, on average, more productive than non-automated firms (Koch et al., 2021), and more productive firms exhibit lower marginal costs and can charge higher markups. To explore this possibility, we augment the model in (7) with a firm-level measure of productivity. Specifically, we use the estimation routine developed by Akerberg et al. (2015) (henceforth ACF) to estimate a flexible output-based translog production function with three inputs (labor, capital, and materials) and robots as an additional input variable. We then run the same set of regressions as before with the firm-level measure of total factor productivity included as an addi-

tional control variable. Table 2 reports the results. We find much smaller point estimates of β than before, such that the markup premium of automated firms is no longer significantly different from zero. We conclude from this exercise that the markup premium of automated over non-automated firms found in Table 1 indeed reflects productivity differences between firms.

Table 2: Pooled sample controlling for productivity (OLS)

	Dependent variable: Markup (in logs)			
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Automated	0.00368 (0.00450)	0.00270 (0.00439)	0.00225 (0.00432)	0.00122 (0.00462)
Industry-year FE	No	Yes	Yes	Nested
Region-year FE	No	No	Yes	Nested
Industry-region-year FE	No	No	No	Yes
Observations	16271	16271	16265	15360
R-squared	0.049	0.112	0.144	0.253

Note: The dependent variable in all regressions is the firm-level markup (in logs). All regressions include the firm’s inputs in logs (labor, capital, and materials) and total factor productivity in logs as control variables. Robust standard errors are clustered at the level of the individual firm and are given in parentheses. *, **, *** denote significance at the 10%, 5%, 1% levels, respectively.

Markup heterogeneity within automated firms.—Above we document average markup differences between automated and non-automated firms. However, our data also allow us to discriminate within the group of automated firms, viz. among those that start automating at some point during our sample period, those that stop automating, and those that automate throughout (i.e., those using robots in each and every year they appear in our sample). This opens up another perspective on the relationship between markups and automation that exploits the time dimension in our data. It also allows us to form expectations about the future evolution of markups within firms, as more and more firms opt to use robots in their production processes over time. We run the following regression, which is similar to the model in (7), but sorts firms into different (mutually exclusive) automation categories:

$$\ln \mu_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 \text{Start}_{it} + \beta_2 \text{Stop}_{it} + \beta_3 \text{Always}_i + \mathbf{X}_{it}^T \boldsymbol{\gamma} + \varepsilon_{it}, \quad (8)$$

where Start_{it} is a 0/1 indicator for a firm that uses robots *for the first time* in year t , Stop_{it} is a 0/1 indicator for an automated firm that stops using robots in year t , and Always_i is a time-constant 0/1 indicator for firms that use robots throughout the sample period. Importantly, the variable Start_{it} is equal to one not just in the first year the firm automates, but also in all subsequent years, and accordingly for Stop_{it} . For convenience, we drop all firms that first switch into and then out of automation (or the other way around).

Table 3 reports the estimation results for the key parameters β_1 , β_2 , and β_3 . As expected, firms automating throughout have a higher average markup than non-automated firms. The specification with the most demanding set of fixed effects in column (4) indicates a markup premium of 1.2 percent. More importantly, firms that start automating also show a markup increase relative to non-automated firms. Their markup premium stands at around 1.5 percent (column (4)). Firms that stop automating exhibit a negative markup premium, but the estimates are not different from zero (in a statistical sense) when looking at column (4) with the full set of fixed effects. These are novel results that speak to the markup dynamics when firms switch from a non-automated production process to an automated one. Importantly, when running the same set of regressions with firm-level productivity (based on ACF) included as a control variable, we do not find significant markup differences for any of the different automation categories; see Table 4. This highlights, again, that productivity is the main driving force behind the markup differences that we find.

Table 3: Start automating — Pooled sample (OLS)

	Dependent variable: Markup (in logs)			
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Start	0.0183*** (0.00503)	0.0164*** (0.00490)	0.0161*** (0.00492)	0.0147*** (0.00550)
Stop	-0.0153* (0.00790)	-0.0167** (0.00762)	-0.0177** (0.00753)	-0.0136 (0.00877)
Always	0.0142*** (0.00519)	0.0166*** (0.00528)	0.0161*** (0.00529)	0.0121** (0.00562)
Industry-year FE	No	Yes	Yes	Nested
Region-year FE	No	No	Yes	Nested
Industry-region-year FE	No	No	No	Yes
Observations	32741	32741	32739	31012
R-squared	0.026	0.093	0.109	0.235

Note: The dependent variable in all regressions is the firm-level markup (in logs). All regressions include the firm's inputs in logs (labor, capital, and materials) as control variables. Robust standard errors are clustered at the level of the individual firm and are given in parentheses. *, **, *** denote significance at the 10%, 5%, 1% levels, respectively.

Differential effects of automation on prices and marginal costs.—We have so far analyzed the relationship between automation and markup *levels*. We have documented novel facts about markup differences between automated and non-automated firms. However, a key virtue of our framework is that we can also disentangle the effects of automation on output prices and marginal costs. We can do this by focusing on *changes* in markups, prices, and marginal costs over time, as detailed in Section 3.2. This is important, as it helps us in understanding, and pinning down, the sources of the markup differences documented above. To do so, we adapt our model in

Table 4: Start automating — Pooled sample controlling for productivity (OLS)

	Dependent variable: Markup (in logs)			
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Start	0.00698 (0.00726)	0.00487 (0.00734)	0.00511 (0.00745)	0.00555 (0.00815)
Stop	-0.00189 (0.0104)	-0.00277 (0.0108)	-0.00462 (0.0104)	-0.000905 (0.0113)
Always	0.00858 (0.00805)	0.00860 (0.00809)	0.00811 (0.00812)	0.00421 (0.00888)
Industry-year FE	No	Yes	Yes	Nested
Region-year FE	No	No	Yes	Nested
Industry-region-year FE	No	No	No	Yes
Observations	12851	12851	12837	11896
R-squared	0.047	0.109	0.140	0.258

Note: The dependent variable in all regressions is the firm-level markup (in logs). All regressions include the firm’s inputs in logs (labor, capital, and materials) and total factor productivity in logs as control variables. Robust standard errors are clustered at the level of the individual firm and are given in parentheses. *,**,*** denote significance at the 10%, 5%, 1% levels, respectively.

(7) as follows:

$$\hat{\Omega}_{it} = \alpha + \beta \text{Automated}_{it} + \mathbf{X}_{it}^T \boldsymbol{\gamma} + \varepsilon_{it}, \quad (9)$$

where $\hat{\Omega}_{it}$ is the percentage change in the markup μ_{it} , the output price P_{it} , or the marginal costs λ_{it} . We stress again that neither the price level nor the level of the marginal costs is observed, but that we can compute the percentage changes from our data (as explained in Section 3.2). Important is also the different interpretation of the estimated coefficients relative to the previous regressions. Since we regress a growth rate on our automation indicator variable, the coefficient β now traces out differences between automated and non-automated firms in how markups, prices, and marginal costs evolve over time rather than differences in levels.

Table 5 reports the results. In all regressions we include the full set of industry-region-year fixed effects as well as the firm’s input factor variables in logs (in first differences, to relate changes in outcomes to changes in input use). We find a significant premium in the markup growth rate for automated firms equal to 0.45 percentage points; see column (1). More importantly, we find negative effects of automation on output prices in column (2) and on marginal costs in column (3), implying that output prices and marginal costs both decrease for automated firms relative to non-automated firms. The relative decrease is stronger for the marginal costs, explaining the markup premium. In columns (4) to (6) we also include the ACF-based measure of firm-level total factor productivity in logs (in first differences). As expected from our previous results, the estimated coefficients become smaller and turn insignificant for the markup and the marginal costs.

Table 5: Changes in markups, prices, and marginal costs

	Dependent variable: Percentage change in the variable given below					
	Markup (1)	Price (2)	MC (3)	Markup (4)	Price (5)	MC (6)
Automated	0.0045*** (0.0014)	-0.0026*** (0.0007)	-0.0072*** (0.0015)	0.0003 (0.0023)	-0.0032*** (0.0011)	-0.0035 (0.0025)
Ind.-region-year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
ln TFP (first diff.)	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	32999	32999	32999	13023	13023	13023
R-squared	0.198	0.254	0.201	0.208	0.246	0.211

Note: The dependent variable is the percentage change in the firm-level markup (columns (1) and (4)), output price (columns (2) and (5)), and marginal cost (columns (3) and (6)), respectively. All regressions include the firm's inputs in logs (labor, capital, and materials) and first differences. Robust standard errors are clustered at the level of the individual firm and are given in parentheses. *, **, *** denote significance at the 10%, 5%, 1% levels, respectively.

Table 6: Start automating — Changes in markups, prices, and marginal costs

	Dependent variable: Percentage change in the variable given below					
	Markup (1)	Price (2)	MC (3)	Markup (4)	Price (5)	MC (6)
Start	0.0036** (0.0017)	-0.0007 (0.0009)	-0.0043** (0.0019)	0.0040 (0.0027)	0.0006 (0.0015)	-0.0034 (0.0030)
Stop	-0.0000 (0.0017)	0.0012 (0.0011)	0.0012 (0.0021)	0.0060** (0.0028)	0.0028 (0.0019)	-0.0031 (0.0034)
Always	0.0034* (0.0020)	-0.0029** (0.0012)	-0.0063*** (0.0024)	0.0003 (0.0029)	-0.0032* (0.0018)	-0.0035 (0.0035)
Ind.-region-year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
ln TFP (first diff.)	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	32999	32999	32999	13023	13023	13023
R-squared	0.198	0.254	0.201	0.208	0.246	0.211

Note: The dependent variable is the percentage change in the firm-level markup (columns (1) and (4)), output price (columns (2) and (5)), and marginal cost (columns (3) and (6)), respectively. All regressions include the firm's inputs in logs (labor, capital, and materials) and first differences. Robust standard errors are clustered at the level of the individual firm and are given in parentheses. *, **, *** denote significance at the 10%, 5%, 1% levels, respectively.

Finally, we again exploit the time dimension of our data to investigate whether automated firms that start or stop using robots in the production process show similar patterns when it comes to the evolution of markups, prices, and marginal costs. Table 6 runs the same set of regressions as before, but now we include Start_{it} , Stop_{it} , and Always_i as right-hand side variables. The results can be summarized as follows. For firms that use robots throughout, we find a pattern of effects that is consistent with the findings in Table 5: prices decrease, but marginal costs decrease even further, so that markups rise (relative to non-automated firms). For firms that start using robots, the effects are similar, although the price decrease is not significantly different from zero. It thus appears that price reductions materialize with some delay following robot adoption. For firms that stop using robots, we find no effects relative to non-automated firms. Finally, and similar to our previous results, once we control for firm-level productivity, most effects turn insignificant.

5 Conclusion

In this paper we have provided new long-run evidence on market concentration, markups, and automation for the interesting case of Spain. The main insights derived from our analysis are as follows. First, firms in Spain find themselves caught up in a tougher and more competitive environment (measured by the number of competing firms). Since this perspective derives from self-reported survey data where firms are free to define the boundaries of the markets they serve, this observation can be explained by a stronger integration of markets across countries (with an increasing total number of competitors in spite of fewer domestic competitors). Importantly, the top firms in the manufacturing sector have seen their market shares stagnate over time. This is consistent with our second finding on rather stable markups for the typical firm in the sample as well as for firms located at the top of the markup distribution. The evidence that we find is, hence, going against some of the evidence found for other countries, especially the U.S., where markups among the top firms have been rising (with significant public and academic concern). Finally, automation comes with higher average markups, an effect that, as we show, is fully explained by the productivity gains associated with automation. Specifically, we find that automation reduces the firm's marginal cost, which translates into a lower output price, but the price reduction is less than proportional, so that the firm's markup rises. This last finding is consistent with less elastic demand and lower passthroughs for more productive firms (Baqae and Farhi, 2020), an assumption that plays a central role in recent literature.

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A Appendix

Figure A.1: Evolution of market shares (1990-2018).[†]

[†]Note: This figure shows the evolution of market shares as reported by firms in the ESEE data. Panels (a) to (d) refer to the firms' 2nd, 3rd, 4th, and 5th most important markets, respectively. Sampling weights apply. Source: Authors' illustration using ESEE data.

Figure A.2: Evolution of market shares of market leaders (1990-2018).[†]

[†]Note: This figure shows the evolution of market shares as reported by firms in the ESEE data. All firms report to be the market leaders in the respective markets. Panels (a) to (d) refer to the firms' 2nd, 3rd, 4th, and 5th most important markets, respectively. Sampling weights apply. Source: Authors' illustration using ESEE data.

Figure A.3: Evolution of market concentration (1990-2018).[†]

[†]Note: This figure shows the evolution of market concentration as reported by firms in the ESEE data. Panels (a) to (d) refer to the firms' 2nd, 3rd, 4th, and 5th most important markets, respectively. Sampling weights apply. *Source:* Authors' illustration using ESEE data.

